

D5.11 Practice abstracts EOP

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

Task 5.11 Cross-exchange

Summary

The major aim of the Thematic Network (TN) EURAKNOS is to boost compiling knowledge for practice by intensifying interaction between various agriculture and forestry networks, thereby maximising the output for practitioners. While WP2 has compiled and evaluated 28 H2020 TNs on data and content impact, the design of the knowledge reservoirs, communication and dissemination strategies, and the multi-actor approach (MAA), WP3 has defined the best practices for TNs to achieve better impact. Task 5.4, part of WP5 "Widen impact of TN knowledge reservoirs", will organise cross-exchange visits between TNs and end-user groups to share best practices for TNs. Task 5.4 will capitalise on the results of WP2 and WP3 and will capture the outcomes in 100 practice abstracts (PAs) in the common format of the European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and sustainability (EIP-AGRI). D5.10 "Practice abstracts Middle of Project (MOP)" represents the first batch of 20 PAs. Besides, this report presents the concept and the structure for the entire 100 PAs, linking the results of the EURAKNOS project and the content of the PAs. The PAs are addressed to end-users. In most TNs, these are farmers, foresters, and advisors. EURAKNOS aims at an optimised exchange of existing MAA, communication, and dissemination methods and tools between the different TNs as well as linked EIP-AGRI Operational Groups (OGs) and H2020 multi-actor projects (MAPs). It seeks a harmonised approach to the establishment of future TNs to maximise the impact on practitioners, farmers, and foresters. Therefore, the PAs focus more on methodology and practical applications for future network participants, coordinators, or leaders. Through the PAs, the resulting innovative knowledge and easily accessible end-user material from this project will be included in the EIP-AGRI website for broad dissemination within the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) community. The end-user material to be produced will contain a considerable number of recommendations for practitioners on the results in the common EIP-AGRI format.

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Content

Content.....	4
List of figures	7
List of tables	7
List of abbreviations and acronyms.....	7
1. Introduction.....	8
1.1. Context	8
1.2. Practice Abstract Guidance	8
1.3. The categorisation of the practice abstracts.....	9
2. Practice Abstracts.....	9
2.1. How to keep a network alive after its end?	16
2.2. How to prepare a co-creation workshop for a digital platform for thematic networks	17
2.3. How to create a future vision for a digital platform of thematic networks.....	18
2.4. How to scope and roadmap a digital platform for thematic networks.....	19
2.5. Key steps in the design of a digital knowledge platform	20
2.6. How to set up an effective digital knowledge reservoir platform?.....	21
2.7. How to create a user-friendly digital platform for thematic networks.....	22
2.8. Use of digital platforms for end-user engagement	23
2.9. How to face the mid-term review of a project.....	24
2.10. How to stimulate peer to peer exchange?	25
2.11. Engaging users in knowledge platforms through training, social media, and discussion forums	26
2.12. Setting up a knowledge repository: the example of Organic Farm Knowledge.....	27
2.13. Thematic Networks (TNs) topic approach.....	28
2.14. Thematic Networks social approach (TNs).....	29
2.15. Producing outputs from thematic networks (TNs).....	30
2.16. Efficiency of TNs: production of outputs.....	31
2.17. TN synergies within the EIP-Agri framework.....	32
2.18. Using search filters and ranking options for customised search results.....	33
2.19. The process of designing online databases.....	34
2.20. The selection of examples for innovation project databases	35
2.21. Defining a set of metadata for annotating data in a centralised repository.....	36
2.22. The visual design of online databases of innovation projects	37
2.23. Language or translation of online databases	38
2.24. Naming conventions to follow for the documents produced by a Thematic Network	39
2.25. Knowledge reservoirs: which design for what purpose?	40
2.26. Setting up a knowledge reservoir: inventory of existing practices	41
2.27. How to improve a knowledge platform: Learning from and with end users	42

2.28.	Enhancing navigation: The example of Organic Farm Knowledge	43
2.29.	How to ensure long-term maintenance of a knowledge platform?.....	44
2.30.	Six recommendations for improved sustainability of Thematic Networks for Agricultural and Forestry Innovation	45
2.31.	The basics of a branding workshop	46
2.32.	Using the knowledge exchange pathways to create higher impact.....	47
2.33.	Recommendations for increasing uptake of your Practice Abstract.....	48
2.34.	Practice Abstracts as a virtual bridge to further project results	49
2.35.	Ten rules for virtual demonstration	50
2.36.	Cross Exchange Visit in virtual mode.....	51
2.37.	How to better engage end-users in online meetings and webinars	52
2.38.	How to communicate efficiently about TN outputs and results in end-user’s demonstration days	53
2.39.	How to organize online meetings which strengthen synergies between different TNs and OGs	54
2.40.	How to better promote end-user surveys using webinars.....	55
2.41.	Relevant dissemination from Thematic Networks (TNs).....	56
2.42.	The ambassador: a key person in the dissemination of knowledge	57
2.43.	Newsletters that generate impact for a TN.....	58
2.44.	How to interpret data from newsletters.....	59
2.45.	More engagement on LinkedIn with your Thematic Network.....	60
2.46.	Engaging content for a successful podcast	61
2.47.	Creating and editing a successful podcast	62
2.48.	How to produce more impactful videos targeting farmers, foresters and advisers	63
2.49.	The TN Explorer’s Guide: flagship product of the EURAKNOS project.....	64
2.50.	Improving the structural organization of the TNs towards more efficient C&D.....	65
2.51.	Enhancing the impact of TNs through professional communication skills and partners..	66
2.52.	Using the right channels & tools for the right target audience.....	67
2.53.	Maximizing the Impact of C&D activities	68
2.54.	What is needed for successful adaptation of good practices?.....	69
	Nemzeti Agrárgazdasági Kamara.....	69
2.55.	Main support and tools after the project?.....	70
	Nemzeti Agrárgazdasági Kamara.....	70
2.56.	Successful online meetings with end users start with good preparation!.....	71
2.57.	Online meetings with end users: Using GoToTraining as a tool.....	72
2.58.	End-user engagement in operational groups and innovative projects	73
2.59.	How to plan a successful consortium meeting.....	74
2.60.	Mobilising networks to optimise health, energy and function	75
2.61.	Facilitating Farmer Led Innovation.....	76

2.62.	Hosting online meetings with end users: How to ensure a smooth running.....	77
2.63.	Organising online meetings with end users: Accounting for end-user needs.....	78
2.64.	How to prepare for networking online as organizer	79
2.65.	How to perform networking online as participants	80
2.66.	Processes behind networking.....	81
2.67.	Why carry out networking?	82
2.68.	How to prepare for networking and get contact during meetings and events	83
2.69.	Co-creation with different actors	84
2.70.	Demonstration as a tool for multi-stakeholder-based co-creation processes.....	85
2.71.	Holding a science and practice meeting as a multi-actor approach	86
2.72.	What kind of competencies an innovation broker needs to fulfil her/his intermediary role? 87	
	Nemzeti Agrárgazdasági Kamara.....	87
2.73.	Why is it important to involve innovation hubs in MA projects?	88
	Nemzeti Agrárgazdasági Kamara.....	88
2.74.	End-users' involvement in the preliminary phases of innovation projects.....	89
2.75.	EU projects focused on livestock: Requests to policymakers	90
2.76.	Learning and collaborating across EU projects focused on livestock.....	91
2.77.	How can stakeholder involvement be enhanced?	92
	Nemzeti Agrárgazdasági Kamara.....	92
2.78.	Setting up innovation groups with farmers.....	93
2.79.	The importance of the interaction between innovation projects.....	94
2.80.	A national initiative to fight grapevine diseases	95
3.	Conclusion and next steps.....	96

List of figures

Figure 1: Practice abstracts’ categories and topics 9

List of tables

Table 1: List of Practice Abstracts 10

List of abbreviations and acronyms

AKIS –Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System

CV – Curriculum vitae

D – Deliverable

EIP-AGRI – European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural productivity and sustainability

EURAKNOS – Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open-Source System

EOP – End of project

KR – Knowledge reservoir

MA – Multi-actor

MAA – Multi-actor approach

MAP –Multi-actor project

MOP – Middle of project

OG – Operational Group

PA – Practice abstract

TN – Thematic Network

WP – Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1. Context

Deliverable 5.11 is an output of Task 5.4 on cross-exchange within WP5 that aims to widen the impact of TN knowledge reservoirs (KRs). This deliverable report reflects the production of 80 practice abstracts (PAs) by the end of the project (EOP) (M27), making it a total of 100 PAs when combined With the 20 PAs presented in D5.10 which was delivered at the mid-point of the EURAKNOS projects. The initial practice abstracts (D5.10) are largely based upon the learnings from WP2 "Compile and evaluate TNs" and WP3 "Design a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir". The 80 PAs included in this Deliverable are based upon the findings of WP4 that explore the feasibility of creating a digital, EU-wide, common KR and will analyse the results of the cross-sectoral and cross-border activities carried out as part of Task 5.4 within WP5.

The PAs follow the EIP-AGRI format, requiring practical information to be conveyed in 1,000-1,500 characters. The purpose of these PAs is to share practical knowledge about content or knowledge collection and storage, communication and dissemination strategies, and the multi-actor approach (MAA) that can be implemented by TNs and other multi-actor projects (MAPs) to interact with their targeted end-users more effectively.

A PA is usually addressed to a specific end-user group, i.e., farmers, foresters, or advisors. In the EURAKNOS project, a second group of end-users can be distinguished, namely coordinators or partners of a TN, or facilitators of a discussion group with a leading function. This explains the selection of topics for the PAs that are mostly dealing with different aspects of TNs, including content or knowledge collection and storage, communication, and dissemination strategies, as well as the MAA from the conceptualisation to the post-project phase. The PAs will help participants of current and future TNs to achieve more impact in terms of reaching and engaging the end-users, and ultimately the uptake of the results by farmers, foresters, and advisors.

1.2. Practice Abstract Guidance

In this section, the framework conditions, and principles for the development of a PA are presented, based on the EIP-AGRI PA guidelines and the EURAKNOS outputs:

- Specifications for structure and format in a PAs: Short and easily understandable title (one key sentence, max 150 characters);
- Summary using easily understandable language (max 1500 char.) = 'practice abstract';
- What problem will the collected or generated knowledge be solved for the end-user? What will be the main benefits to the practitioner?
- Main outcome/recommendation (2-3 main results);
- Contact data author (institution, e-mail), project funding information, link to the project website

Guidelines for the selection of an appropriate theme for the PA:

- Choose the right topic: the content needs to be assessed against their potential to bring concrete recommendations and useful results for practice (i.e. information/tools that practitioners can immediately use);

- Consider the appropriate level of detail: to identify practical information it is useful to focus on the level of work packages or tasks, rather than to try to summarise the project itself to find practice-relevant information
- Focus on useable results: the main scope is to focus on results, outcomes, and recommendations that can 'be used' and move the practitioner to action. Avoid describing project activities since these are of no further use for the reader at the time he/she is reading it;
- Take advantage: use already available and relevant information from your project. The sometimes short, concise and ready-to-use information is already available for the target audience on your website or in reported deliverables
- Appropriate presentation: It is key to put yourself in the place of the reader (end-user) when writing. What do they want to read about? What would practitioners find useful? Would they disengage when reading this sentence?

1.3. The categorisation of the practice abstracts

The structure for the categorisation of all PAs was adapted from D2.5. In WP2, main categories were defined that build the basic framework for the optimised development of a TN which formed the basis for the further work in WP3, whereas WP4 mainly relates to TN content storage. Additionally, subcategories were defined to derive a higher benefit from the use in TNs. Finally, the PAs were classified into these subcategories or topics.

TN content <i>creation of outputs</i>	TN content storage <i>how outputs are stored</i>	TN Communication & Dissemination <i>uptake and promotion of outputs</i>	TN multi-actor approach <i>who to involve and how.</i>	TN Best Practice Examples
TN Purpose	TN Purpose	TN Resources Dissemination	TN Structure:	TN Livestock
TN State of The Art:	TN Output Standardisation	TN Output Format	TN Fasilitasiion	TN Crops
TN Content	TN Sustainability	TN Peer-To-Peer Exchange	TN Roadmap:	TN Horizontal Themes
TN Digital Support	TN Digital Support	TN Assets Leveraging	TN Digital Support	TN Forestry
TN User Interaction	TN User Interaction	TN Training	TN User Interaction	
TN Digital Platform	TN Digital Platform	TN Digital Platform	TN Digital Platform	
	TN Separate Communication & Dissemination	TN Community of Practice	TN Community of Practice	
		TN Separate Communication & Dissemination	TN Culture:	
		Access to TN Output		

Figure 1: Practice abstracts' categories and topics

2. Practice Abstracts

The first 20 PAs produced by the EURAKNOS project were mainly based on findings of WP2 and were developed with the support of all partners. These PAs, together with the 80 additional PAs, contribute to the development of the TNs. Together with the TN Explorer's Guide (D3.6), a major output of WP3, they form a basic manual for TNs to be more effective and to achieve better impact. In addition to the categories from WP2 (content, content storage, communication and dissemination, and MAA), PAs based on best practices of TNs are also provided. These are intended to serve as concrete examples for running TNs or those currently being developed.

Table 1 lists the PAs by category and topic as well as title and responsible partner. Below the table, the separate PAs are presented. **All practice abstracts are available for download via the EIP-AGRI portal¹ as well as the EURAKNOS project homepage².**

Table 1: List of Practice Abstracts

No.	Category	Topic	Practice Abstract Title	Responsible Partner
1	TN content, TN Storage	TN Content;TN purpose	How to keep a network alive after its end?	IFV
2	TN Content	TN digital support	How to prepare a co-creation workshop for a digital platform for thematic networks	LFG
3	TN Content, TN content storage	TN user interaction	How to create a future vision for a digital platform of thematic networks	LFG
4	TN Content, TN content storage	TN digital support	How to scope and roadmap a digital platform for thematic networks	LFG
5	TN content storage	TN outputs standardization	Key steps in the design of a digital knowledge platform	IDELE
6	TN content storage	TN digital platform	How to set up an effective digital knowledge reservoir platform?	IFOAM Organics Europe
7	TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA	TN digital platform; TN community of practice	How to create a user-friendly digital platform for thematic networks	LFG
8	TN Content, TN MAA	TN digital platform	Use of digital platforms for end-user engagement	UGent
9	TN Content, TN communication and dissemination	TN Content; Access to TN outputs	How to face the mid-term review of a project	UGent
10	TN Content, TN communication and dissemination	TN peer to ;peer exchange TN user interaction	How to stimulate peer to peer exchange?	IFV
11	TN content; TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA	TN end-user interaction, TN digital platform; TN resource dissemination, TN output format, TN peer-to-peer exchange, TN training, TN community of practice, access to TN outputs; TN facilitation, TN digital support	Engaging users in knowledge platforms through training, social media and discussion forums	IFOAM Organics Europe

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/>

² www.euraknos.eu

12	TN content; TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA; TN best practice examples	TN digital platform; access to TN outputs; TN horizontal themes	Setting up a knowledge repository: the example of Organic Farm Knowledge	IFOAM Organics Europe
13	TN content; TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA	TN outputs standardization	Thematic Networks (TNs) topic approach	USC
14	TN content; TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA	TN outputs standardization	Thematic Networks social approach (TNs)	USC
15	TN content; TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA	TN outputs standardization	Producing outputs from thematic networks (TNs)	USC
16	TN content; TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA	TN outputs standardization	Efficiency of TNs: production of outputs	USC
17	TN content; TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA	TN outputs standardization	TN synergies within the EIP-Agri framework	USC
18	TN content storage	TN digital platform	Using search filters and ranking options for customised search results	AUA
19	TN content storage	TN user interaction	The process of designing online databases	ARC
20	TN content storage	TN sustainability	The selection of examples for innovation project databases	ARC
21	TN content storage	TN digital platform	Defining a set of metadata for annotating data in a centralised repository	AUA
22	TN content storage	TN digital platform	The visual design of online databases of innovation projects	ARC
23	TN content storage	TN user interaction	Language or translation of online databases	ARC
24	TN content storage	TN digital platform	Naming conventions to follow for the documents produced by a Thematic Network	AUA
25	TN content storage	TN digital platform	Knowledge reservoirs: which design for what purpose?	IDELE
26	TN content storage	TN purpose	Setting up a knowledge reservoir: inventory of existing practices	IDELE
27	TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA	TN digital platform; TN community of practice	How to improve a knowledge platform: Learning from and with end users	IFOAM Organics Europe
28	TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA; TN best practice examples	TN digital platform; access to TN outputs; TN digital support; TN horizontal themes	Enhancing navigation: The example of Organic Farm Knowledge	IFOAM Organics Europe

29	TN content storage; TN C&D; TN MAA; TN best practice examples	TN digital platform; TN sustainability; TN training, access to TN outputs; TN roadmap, TN digital support; TN horizontal themes	How to ensure long-term maintenance of a knowledge platform?	IFOAM Organics Europe
30	TN content storage; TN MAA	TN sustainability; TN structure; TN roadmap; TN digital structure; TN digital support	Six recommendations for improved sustainability of Thematic Networks for Agricultural and Forestry Innovation	IfA
31	TN communication and dissemination	TN outputs standardization	The basics of a branding workshop	LFG
32	TN communication and dissemination	TN resource dissemination	Using the knowledge exchange pathways to create higher impact	RAU
33	TN communication and dissemination	TN peer to peer exchange	Recommendations for increasing uptake of your Practice Abstract	RAU
34	TN communication and dissemination	TN peer to peer exchange	Practice Abstracts as a virtual bridge to further project results	RAU
35	TN communication and dissemination	TN peer to peer exchange; TN digital support	Ten rules for virtual demonstration	IFV
36	TN communication and dissemination	TN peer to peer exchange	Cross Exchange Visit in virtual mode	ARC
37	TN communication and dissemination	access to TN outputs	How to better engage end-users in online meetings and webinars	GLZ
38	TN communication and dissemination	access to TN outputs	How to communicate efficiently about TN outputs and results in end-user's demonstration days	GLZ
39	TN communication and dissemination	TN peer to peer exchange	How to organize online meetings which strengthen synergies between different TNs and Ogs	GLZ
40	TN communication and dissemination	TN peer to peer exchange	How to better promote end-user surveys using webinars	GLZ
41	TN communication and dissemination	TN training	Relevant dissemination from Thematic Networks (TNs)	PSKW

42	TN communication and dissemination	TN peer to peer exchange	The ambassador: a key person in the dissemination of knowledge	IDELE
43	TN communication and dissemination	TN training; TN digital platform	Newsletters that generate impact for a TN	PSKW
44	TN communication and dissemination	TN training; TN digital platform	How to interpret data from newsletters	PSKW
45	TN communication and dissemination	TN training; TN digital platform	More engagement on LinkedIn with your Thematic Network	PSKW
46	TN communication and dissemination	TN Output format; TN resources dissemination	Engaging content for a successful podcast	IfA
47	TN communication and dissemination	TN Output format; TN resources dissemination	Creating and editing a successful podcast	IfA
48	TN communication and dissemination	access to TN outputs	How to produce more impactful videos targeting farmers, foresters and advisers	GLZ
49	TN communication and dissemination	access to TN outputs	The TN Explorer's Guide: flagship product of the EURAKNOS project	IDELE
50	TN communication and dissemination	access to TN outputs	Improving the structural organization of the TNs towards more efficient C&D	ACTA
51	TN communication and dissemination	TN training; TN facilitation	Enhancing the impact of TNs through professional communication skills and partners	ACTA
52	TN Communication and dissemination	TN output format; TN community of practice	Using the right channels & tools for the right target audience	ACTA
53	TN communication and dissemination	TN resource dissemination	Maximizing the Impact of C&D activities	ACTA
54	TN communication and dissemination	TN assets leveraging	What is needed for successful adaptation of good practices?	NAK
55	TN communication and dissemination; TN MAA	access to TN outputs; TN content; TN user interaction	Main support and tools after the project?	NAK

56	TN Communication and Dissemination; TN MAA	TN resource dissemination, TN peer-to- peer exchange; TN digital support, TN facilitation, TN user interaction	Successful online meetings with end users start with good preparation!	IFOAM Organics Europe
57	TN Communication and Dissemination; TN MAA	TN resource dissemination; TN peer-to- peer exchange; TN digital support; TN facilitation; TN user interaction	Online meetings with end users: Using GoToTraining as a tool	IFOAM Organics Europe
58	TN MAA	TN user interaction	End-user engagement in operational groups and innovative projects	UGent
59	TN MAA	TN facilitation	How to plan a successful consortium meeting	UGent
60	TN MAA	TN structure	Mobilising networks to optimise health, energy and function	RAU
61	TN MAA	TN facilitation	Facilitating Farmer Led Innovation	RAU
62	TN MAA	TN digital support	Hosting online meetings with end users: How to ensure a smooth running	IFOAM Organics Europe
63	TN MAA	TN digital support; TN facilitation; TN user interaction	Organising online meetings with end users: Accounting for end-user needs	IFOAM Organics Europe
64	TN MAA	TN user interaction; TN roadmap	How to prepare for networking online as organizer	AU
65	TN MAA	TN user interaction; TN roadmap	How to perform networking online as participants	AU
66	TN MAA	TN user interaction	Processes behind networking	AU
67	TN MAA	TN user interaction	Why carry out networking?	AU
68	TN MAA	TN digital support	How to prepare for networking and get contact during meetings and events	AU
69	TN MAA	TN user interaction; TN facilitation	Co-creation with different actors	GLZ
70	TN MAA	TN user interaction; TN facilitation	Demonstration as a tool for multi-stakeholder- based co-creation processes	GLZ
71	TN MAA	TN user interaction; TN facilitation	Holding a science and practice meeting as a multi-actor approach	GLZ
72	TN MAA	TN training; TN facilitation	What kind of competencies an innovation broker needs to fulfil her/his intermediary role?	NAK
73	TN MAA, TN Communication and dissemination	TN user interaction; TN facilitation; TN peer to peer exchange	Why is important to involve innovation hubs in MA projects?	NAK

74	TN MAA, TN Content	TN user interaction; TN peer-to-peer exchange; TN community of practice	End-users' involvement in the preliminary phases of innovation projects	UGent
75	TN MAA	TN sustainability; TN structure; TN roadmap; TN digital structure	EU projects focused on livestock: Requests to policymakers	IfA
76	TN MAA	TN sustainability; TN structure; TN roadmap; TN digital structure	Learning and collaborating across EU projects focused on livestock	IfA
77	TN MAA	TN user interaction; TN facilitation	How can stakeholder involvement be enhanced?	NAK
78	TN MAA; TN best practice examples	TN structure; TN facilitation; TN community of practice; TN horizontal themes	Setting up innovation groups with farmers	IFOAM Organics Europe
79	TN MAA; TN communication and dissemination	TN user interaction; TN peer-to-peer exchange	The importance of the interaction between innovation projects	UGent
80	TN best practices examples	TN crops	A national initiative to fight grapevine diseases	IFV

2.1. How to keep a network alive after its end?

During a thematic network, a lot of outputs are produced and are often hosted in a dedicated website or platform, namely a knowledge reservoir (for example : <http://www.winetwork-data.eu/en/gb/default.asp#>). After a network ends, there is no more funding or dedicated time and activity, so maintaining the platform is difficult. Who pays for website maintenance? For how long? A TN cannot commit to sustainability despite the desire to perpetuate the knowledge acquired. To keep the platform functional after the project ends, the platform must be hosted on an existing information site which is intended to last over time, and which can be financed in other ways. When the platform is independent, content may be preserved in the EUREKA platform (<https://h2020eureka.eu/>).

Furthermore, a network lives by a continuous flow of information. This flow must be backed up and regularly fed. After a network ends, partners must disseminate documents produced in the framework of the project work by their own means.

Synergies with other projects and other websites need to be created during the network's life. It will allow the dissemination to continue even after the project ends, by disseminating project results on other websites and within new networks.

Using social networks is an easy way to keep a network alive. Indeed, it's easy to retweet and like interesting information. Continuous activity on social network will keep the end-users involved in the project and its topic.

Finally, partners should continue to participate in workshops and conferences to share their experience in the project, disseminate results and encourage their peers to lead thematic networks. A project stays alive thanks to the quality of the outputs, its continuous flow of information and its reputation in the scientific and industry communities and beyond.

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2.2. How to prepare a co-creation workshop for a digital platform for thematic networks

Creating a digital platform for thematic networks benefits greatly from their input with regard to what their needs are, how they interact with the end-users of their content and potential obstacles that might occur.

In order to collect this information, the format of a co-creation workshop, in which all relevant stakeholders (thematic network coordinators, researchers, farmers, foresters, advisors, policy makers and digital developers) are involved is well suited. During co-creation workshops, such as the EURAKNOS workshops in Budapest and Paris, a facilitator will inquire about the expectations and needs of the different stakeholders, align these expectations and create a common understanding, present examples of other platforms and ask the different stakeholders to provide feedback with regard to what they find useful and what may cause them frustration. Of additional importance is to properly explain the process of developing a digital platform to the different stakeholders and discuss potential obstacles with them as was done during the EURAKNOS consortium meeting in Athens.

The length of the workshop depends on several factors such as the number of participants, the amount of feedback that is expected of every stakeholder and the availability of the different stakeholders. Finally, a co-creation workshop can be conducted physically, digitally or a combination of both.

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2.3. How to create a future vision for a digital platform of thematic networks

Creating a vision for a future digital platform is less evident than it may seem:

- [Research](#) has shown that people don't know what they want until you put it in front of them;
- Most people are also not used to turning an abstract idea of the future into a concrete product in the here and now;
- A digital platform isn't independent of the other activities thematic networks are involved in.

In order to facilitate this process, during the EURAKNOS consortium meeting we started out by asking the consortium members a series of questions related to the goal and purpose of the digital platform. Subsequently, during the EURAKNOS Budapest workshop (September 2019) we asked potential end-users (farmers, foresters, advisors and researchers) what some of the biggest challenges they were facing now in agriculture and thematic networks in order to detect which needs the digital platform would need to meet. Next, we asked them to individually write a short article about the ideal thematic network, what kind of information it would offer, how it would communicate, how it would engage with end-users, what their digital platform would look like etc. This information was then summarized by a facilitator into the cover of a magazine to allow end-users to imagine this thematic network and its platform more concretely. This information was distilled into recommendations for thematic networks and their future platform.

Example of a cover by a group during the EURAKNOS Budapest workshop

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2.4. How to scope and roadmap a digital platform for thematic networks

Creating a digital platform involves making some difficult decisions on what to include and when to introduce it. The digital world rapidly evolves, and so do the expectations of the end-users (e.g., farmers, foresters, advisors).

In order to be able to meet these expectations and remain within budget, we created a vision for the future platform which includes potential features and information, which we then start prioritizing. It is important to have an overall view of what might finally be included in the platform to aid with this prioritization (e.g. if users will have to be able to provide feedback on content, it is important that the content is first made available in a user-friendly way, otherwise users might not use the platform).

In order to define the scope of the project, it is important to take into consideration the available budget, time, personnel, made agreements and user requirements. In EURAKNOS this scoping and road mapping exercise was done with consortium members (such as the project coordination team) who have access and an overview of all needed project and technical information to allow for the future vision to be divided up into different phases, each containing necessary features as well as nice to have features. This will allow for a more flexible approach to dealing with changing expectations of end-users.

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2.5. Key steps in the design of a digital knowledge platform

To set up an effective digital knowledge platform, consider the following critical aspects:

1. During the value creation process:
 - What is the purpose of creating the platform?
 - What is the innovation compared to the existing one?
 - Who are the targets, the future end-users?
 - What service is proposed?
 - What are the expectations of potential users?
 - What resources can be mobilised (human, financial, time)?
 - Who should the platform serve? For what purposes?
2. During the design process:
 - Who will create the platform? And how? Following which steps?
 - What are the detailed specifications expected from the future platform?
3. During the business modelling:
 - What is the budget allocated for development?
 - What is the budget allocated for operation and future maintenance?
 - Who produces the tool: in-house expertise or an external service provider?
 - i. What level of service is needed?
 - ii. Within what timeframe?
 - iii. What type of collaboration is needed?
 - iv. What are the costs?
 - Who ensures that deadlines are met?
4. During the deployment process:
 - Who manages the platform?
 - Does it require special training?
 - How to promote the platform?
 - What maintenance is required?

Following these steps will ensure a successful digital knowledge platform is created.

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2.6. How to set up an effective digital knowledge reservoir platform?

To set up a digital platform that makes your project results and knowledge widely available, start with clearly defining the context, objectives, and users to be reached. During the design process, pay attention to the following points:

- **Content:** For high impact in terms of uptake of results by the users, make sure the knowledge stored on the platform is of high relevance, easily accessible, and understandable. Ensure a quality review of the content. Content and presentation should match.
- **Multi-actor approach:** Involve end users in the design of a user-friendly interface. Develop a prototype that can be presented to users with different profiles. Collect feedback through surveys and tests and use it to improve the platform.
- **FAIR data principles:** Make both data and metadata (data that provide a structured description of the data on the platform) findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A complete, detailed, and coherent metadata structure is the basis for an effective and user-friendly search function and supports users in their navigation.
- **Focus on those communication channels that are most frequented by the users** (for example newsletter, contact info).
- **Monitoring:** Use specific quantitative and qualitative indicators to evaluate the success and impact of your project results, such as the number of interactions on the platform, downloads, and comments.
- **Self-supporting system:** Ensure resources to maintain the platform.
- **Later, you can add new functionalities, such as a login function with personalisation and user recommendations or specific (thematic) user communities.**

Get inspired by other projects' knowledge bases, for example FERTINNOWA:
<https://www.fertinnowa.com/technology-database/>

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2.7. How to create a user-friendly digital platform for thematic networks

Making a knowledge platform that is user-friendly to end-users is not an easy job. Not every target population (e.g. farmer, foresters, advisors) has the same needs, and more often they have difficulties expressing these needs in ways software developers can understand them. Involving a user-researcher into the project will allow you to detect the problems your target-population is dealing with and together with members of this target population they will come up with possible solutions when creating the digital platform through workshops (e.g. the EURAKNOS workshops in Budapest and Paris), interviews and surveys as well as an information architecture of the kinds of webpages the platform will need (e.g. a homepage, contact page, etc.).

The UX-designer (user experience) uses this information to rapidly design a draft concept of the platform in the form of a clickable prototype (compare it to a PowerPoint presentation which looks and feels like a website). The user-researcher will present this prototype to 5-6 potential end-users (e.g. farmers) in order to get feedback and [detect 80%](#) of the most common errors in the prototype (e.g. the menu doesn't use the right categories, the homepage doesn't put the most important information first, etc.). Subsequently, the UX-designer will use this information to improve the prototype so it can be presented to 6 different end-users to verify whether the same issues get mentioned, and/or new (smaller) issues present themselves. By working in this iterative way, we avoid creating a fully developed platform which will not be user-friendly and have very little options to change as the development-phase of a platform is less flexible and the cost of this phase is most often the biggest one.

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2.8. Use of digital platforms for end-user engagement

During the cross-exchange visit on Smart protection in the frame of the EURAKNOS project, a point of discussion was the use of digital platforms to engage end-users.

If used in a proper way, digital platforms can be a powerful and efficient tool to engage end-user groups. Especially if they can contribute to materials, they find useful and relevant for their activity in the platform. An example is given by the platform of the TN Innoseta. Once uploaded, the material is verified not only by researchers but also directly by farmers during workshops (at national and international levels). Another example of a good end-user engagement platform is from the project IPM Decisions (<https://www.ipmdecisions.net/>). At the beginning of this project, a series of workshops with 375 participants were organized. It was possible to collect participants' needs and their initial ideas through the platform. Furthermore, a panel that involved farmers and advisors from 12 countries was created and consulted to organize inputs in the development stage of the platform.

These two examples highlighted that actively involving farmers at a very early stage of the project is fundamental. Building an EU network of farmers and advisors remains a challenge. In the Thematic Network, Innoseta, the involvement of local farmers associations as key intermediaries was encouraged. As they are directly in contact with farmers, it will be easier to engage them in project activities, hence reinforcing the local network and impact of the project's outputs.

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2.9. How to face the mid-term review of a project

EURAKNOS is a relatively short project, only two years. This means that the project has a fast pace and therefore the mid-term review came around quickly in January 2020. As the project involves several actors, their participation was essential for the success of the mid-term review.

The evaluation itself was a very challenging moment. During the discussion with the European Commission reviewers, many aspects of the project were assessed and constructively criticized. Thanks to the involvement of a Strategic Innovation Board, we were able to better address the criticisms and include aspects that we had not considered before.

While preparing the mid-term review the first aspect is to engage WP leaders and task contributors. It is an essential aspect as they can contribute concrete examples and detailed descriptions of the tasks that were performed. Most importantly, the information needs to be presented in a standardized way. This can be achieved by distributing a pre-made document so that each partner can fill in their contribution to the report.

Another important aspect is to strictly follow the template of the European Commission and be concise, avoiding repetitions. The reviewers are already aware of what the project is about. Instead of repeating task description, it is important to focus on the objectives and achievements.

The final suggestion is to take the criticisms constructively because they are made to improve the work.

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2.10. How to stimulate peer to peer exchange?

Based on with ready-to-use knowledge, peer to peer exchange improves the learning process. However, this type of exchange needs to be stimulated to be effective (<https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/5-learning-and-facilitation-methods/>).

- Participants must be engaged in pro-active exchanges. Giving participants the opportunity to share their experience, preferably in small groups or workshops, increases practical knowledge uptake. Encouraging informal exchanges and providing sufficient time for farmers to talk together are key to success. The wider the range of experiences and the more surprised the participants are, the more participants exchange with peers. Experiencing a variety of practical activities, such as field visits, sharing observations of practical demonstrations with a facilitator will enhance understanding, learning and interaction amongst participants. The venue should be set up so that everyone can comfortably listen and exchange with the facilitator and participants.
- A variety of learning methods can be used during demonstration events, e.g., posters, presentations and lectures, experiments, discussions, workshops, etc. These activities vary in the degree of interaction between demonstrators and participants, and the active engagement required from farmers, and call for different learning styles.
- The choice of which combination of learning methods to adopt depends on the objective, as well as the group size and composition. Specific tools may be used to increase interaction and enhance the learning experience, such as voting systems or interactive applications (e.g. www.mentimeter.com and <https://kahoot.com/>), videos or visuals (such as www.canva.com) and the distribution of additional information (booklets, reports) to take home.

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2.11. Engaging users in knowledge platforms through training, social media, and discussion forums

Online training courses, webinars, social media and/or a discussion forum integrated in your knowledge platform can be effective tools for learning and sharing knowledge and information. Leveraging good practices through training and education will enhance your project's exploitation and therefore impact.

- Ensure good planning, organisation, and facilitation.
- Offer the possibility to ask questions, add valuable information, discuss with each other, and comment in the chat.
- Use the material provided, such as new knowledge, tools and (audio-)visual media for trainings to add value to your platform and to ensure its long-term maintenance.
- Integrate further interactive elements such as polls in live events to engage with the participants.
- Complement events with a permanent online discussion forum where users can ask questions and bring in their own knowledge and experiences while getting reliable information from experts and colleagues. This could also be a mobile app with good promotion, for example through farmers' magazines. Consider consolidating all the comments in the form of a document, handbook, or video.
- Evaluate the number of training modules, downloads, and persons using them to measure the impact.

Check the TN Explorer's Guide for more practical tips:

<https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/Explorers-guide-interactive-EN-FINAL.pdf>

Also have a look at these TN facilitation manuals:

- AgriSpin Training Toolkit: <https://agrispin.eu/training-toolkit/>
- Hennovation Practice-Led Innovation networks in agriculture: a guide for facilitators: <http://hennovation.eu/facilitating%20practiceled%20innovation/facilitation%20guidelines.html>

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2.12. Setting up a knowledge repository: the example of Organic Farm Knowledge

If you intend to set up a digital repository that hosts your project's knowledge outputs, the online platform Organic Farm Knowledge (<https://organic-farmknowledge.org/>) can serve as an example. It provides access to a range of tools and resources about organic farming that help to improve production, while also aiming to serve as a virtual meeting place for cross-border learning. An introduction video to the platform will soon be available here: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCKA7iMg-_4SxmWbxYQzfjEw

1. Provide a clear structure to guide the user, reducing the time spent on finding the right information.
 - a. Minimise the number of sections.
 - b. Facilitate the search for specific tools or solutions through a good search function with filters that allow searching for a specific theme and/or type of tool (e.g., video) and/or by keywords, country of origin, organisation, project, year, and language.
2. Once the structure is clear, check the content:
 - a. The outputs should be based on practical expertise.
 - b. The content should be tailored to the profile and level of expertise of the individual user, available in the preferred language and format. A responsive digital platform with automatic profiling and translation creates trust, which in turn can amplify the impact and number of users reached.
 - c. Output formats should be visual and interactive, for example engaging videos of best practices.
 - d. In the dissemination strategy, take into account the context, audience, and capacity of your TN.
 - e. Involve the end users through a discussion forum or social media integrated in the platform to enable knowledge sharing and discussion.
 - f. Consider asking users to help with the translation of knowledge into understandable language and formats.

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2.13. Thematic Networks (TNs) topic approach

The EIP-Agri thematic networks are an excellent tool for farmers to find updated information about different topics in rural areas but also dealing with urban and peri-urban areas.

The promotion of the connections between the urban and rural areas is seen as necessary to increase land use sustainability across Europe. They are usually based on a set of multi-actor networks including relevant actors developing information around a specific topic.

The EURAKNOS analysis of the current thematic networks showed a large number of topics dealing with crops, followed by livestock, and with many fewer on forestry and agroforestry, following the short financial incomes provided by the rural sectors. The amount of searchable data integrated by the whole thematic networks were over 4500 at the end of 2018, with more than 95% dealing with agriculture and the rest linked to forestry and agroforestry.

Very few thematic networks are linked to the development of land and market interactions such as the landscape scales or the market scales (value chains) associated with the multipurpose of the land providing a sustainable holistic approach. More thematic networks working at interaction level (landscape, value chains) are needed to increase resource use efficiency and sustainability linked to economic, environment and social aspects.

More information:

https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/D2.1_20200531_Report_on_content_and_structures.pdf

<https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/about/thematic-networks-%E2%80%93-closing-research-and>

https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/eip-agri_brochure_thematic_networks_2016_en_web.pdf

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2.14. Thematic Networks social approach (TNs)

Thematic Networks (TNs) are excellent tools designed by EIP-Agri to foster innovation across Europe. Farming systems in Europe are quite diverse considering farmer gender predominance, allocated time, degree of collaboration, farm size, and type of farming systems.

EU farming is a very male dominated profession (28% of farmers women in 2016) making it necessary to increase the role of “official” women working in the farms, usually not recognized. The whole TNs tackle specifically women aspects alone (54.5%) or combined with men (45.5%) as part of their aims.

The lack of precise official estimates about part-time workers on farms is also relevant since most of funds are allocated to full-time workers and do not consider part-time farmers. Around 80% of TNs foster innovations thinking on part time farmers, while all of them deal with full time workers. Farmers’ organizations linked to cooperatives, family farming and collective farming is considered together by 67% of TNs, while only 14% targets one of these three groups, making a good representation of farming types.

Most of the TNs deal with large farms (87%) with a low extent associated with small farming systems (78%). Finally, most TNs work with Conventional (73%) and organic (64%) farming systems while few work with precision farming (32%), mixed farming (32%), conservation (32%) and low input (36.4%) agriculture.

More information:

https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/D2.1_20200531_Report_on_content_and_structures.pdf

Eurostat 2018 Farmers & agricultural labour force statistics.

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Farmers_and_the_agricultural_labour_force_statistics&oldid=431368

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2.15. Producing outputs from thematic networks (TNs)

Producing innovation outputs in EIP-Agri TNs should be based on all actors' knowledge to solve the main challenges experienced by most farmers in the EU population.

Most TN data was from researchers (92% of the TN), farmers (87.5%) and advisors (75%) fulfilling the aim of gathering all most relevant available information. This information was mainly gathered through the partnership activities (87.5%: literature review) but also through workshops (87.5%), interviews (71%) and benchmarking (21%).

Information was delivered as practice abstracts (87.5%) which is a cost-effective way of showing interesting ideas to overcome farmers' challenges but also through visual summaries such as Factsheets (83.3%). Longer documents where farmers can find most of the relevant information for their farms such as Technical articles (67%), Handbooks (54%), Guides (45%), booklets (45%) were also produced. Researchers and advisors were also an important target group reached through research papers (75%) or reviews (71%). At lower extent, information was also released as videos (42%) probably due to the high cost it has. Communication was also seen as key to show up the results of the TN, being the 79% communicating their results as press releases, 33.3% as pictures and the 20.8% as podcasts.

Most relevant output types were considered by the TNs, however greater effort should be made to develop more audiovisual material.

More info:

https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/sites/default/files/eip-agri_brochure_thematic_networks_2016_en_web.pdf

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2.16. Efficiency of TNs: production of outputs

Producing materials to provide farmers with insights aimed at improving sustainability should consider the number of end-users reached and the cost of the materials produced.

TNs produce around 8 different types of materials (mostly practice abstracts, factsheets, press releases, research papers, reviews, technical articles, handbooks, reports and guides). TN partnerships considered the production of guides as a very effort-demanding activity (due to the production of a long and illustrated document) followed by the practice abstracts (due to the large number of Practice Abstracts that are produced), videos and factsheets (due to the need of several experts to produce it). On the contrary, communication (press releases and podcasts) is the activity with less effort, something that should change if the sustainable agriculture is seen as an activity that should modify the consumer patterns and therefore the knowledge that consumers have about sustainability.

When a farmer challenge is proposed, the innovation development as a written or audiovisual output created to overcome the challenge is usually subject to limiting factors. Lack of time is the most limiting factor, followed by lack of information, lack of budget among others (existing tools, time for translation, qualified technology and product, farmers fatigue when interviewed). The lack of translated materials to languages other than English is declared as a huge barrier to spread the knowledge.

More info:

<https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/Explorers-guide-EN-interactive.pdf>

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2.17. TN synergies within the EIP-Agri framework

TNs are part of the EIP-Agri activities that should be associated with a practice abstracts (PA) repository and operational groups (OGs) linked to National Rural Networks (NRN) activities. The PA repository is fed by the TN and the OGs.

EURAKNOS analysed the global content of these activities by counting the most frequent words appearing in almost 4000 outputs. Arable crops are tackled by 45.5% of the TN and 35.6% of the OGs. Arable OGs seem to be more related to holistic management of arable lands while the practice abstracts and the TN seem to be more connected with specific plot-practices, as they aim to solve specific plot management challenges. Around 32% of the TNs and 42% of the OGs dealt with permanent grasslands. Permanent grasslands OGs seem to have a more holistic approach while PA are more focused on specific farms and TN in the ecosystem services delivery of farms.

Most of the TNs described that they are or were not able to make strong connections to other initiatives in the EIP-Agri landscape. However, they declared that good connections are taken place with multi-actor approach projects. Topics of the OGs seem to have a more holistic approach, considering the farms as a whole, while practice abstracts are related to specific plot management and finally TNs consider the ecosystem services and delivery of those global or specific practices.

More information:

<https://open.spotify.com/episode/31SGWF7UGOJg4fAtQ481GI>

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2.18. Using search filters and ranking options for customised search results

When delivering data through a centralised repository, the end user needs to be able to easily search for the information they require. Metadata are annotations (i.e., descriptions) of the data which facilitate the process of data searches and ensures that the user will get relevant results. However, in many cases a large number of results are obtained. Another issue that the order in which the results are presented may not be the desired one. To either limit the number of search results or change their order, we use filtering and ranking options.

Search filters are options which can be selected by the user by ticking a check box. Imagine someone visiting a centralised repository of agricultural data searching for digital content about precision farming technologies. That person may only be interested in content available as presentations. By ticking in the check box next to the filtering option ‘presentations’, the user will be able to retrieve content about precision farming technologies available as presentations.

Ranking relates to the order in which results are displayed. Search results can be ranked in an alphabetical or chronological order, with regard to user ratings or in terms of their relevance to the search query (algorithms like PageRank are used for this purpose).

To enhance the user experience, both filtering and result ranking options should be considered. The initial attempts to address this issue in EURAKNOS are reported in Deliverable 4.3.

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2.19. The process of designing online databases

Commonly, thematic networks are collecting and presenting a large variety of materials on their websites as knowledge reservoirs. How to build reliable database or knowledge reservoir? Which one is more useful for the end-users?

Step 1: the need for a database.

The process of creating databases consisting of innovative practice examples is usually top-down oriented. The formal obligation to share and publish information about project results ends up with low-value information, "about". In practice, these websites are just a catalogue of projects.

Step 2: beneficiaries.

The project catalogues are important for those users who are already busy with projects and are curious about new ideas; but practitioners' needs are rather oriented to results and lessons learned. To find out the expectations, you must first get to know who your target group is, but this may turn out to be a rather tricky question. Depending on if your target is e.g. farmers, advisors or public servants, their needs may vary significantly.

Step 3: listen to the user.

One way to ascertain the user needs is to circulate a survey, but more useful is user testing. The fruitful end-user's experience relies on the relationship between user and website administrator. The information may seem clearly understandable to the website designer, but not for the user. The feedback loop is a natural process of any product or service design.

Although the target group may be practitioners, advisors and innovation managers are the mediators in receiving feedback. They can be consulted more actively than farmers.

Lesson learned: Pick out your own critical viewer and build a relationship with him/her!

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2.20. The selection of examples for innovation project databases

Thematic networks and innovation support services are collecting and presenting a large variety of information on their websites. What kind of materials will make the database useful and manageable?

If the aim is to publish all the available information, it seems to be a huge task, which soon becomes a burden. The amount of information on the internet is growing and people use keywords rather than search whole information using one concrete website.

Step 1: Make a decision – what is the main force to have a database.

Databases for national rural networks' Innovation projects rarely have specific criteria for the selection of examples. Every relevant project, from the website managers' point of view, regarding the **national** innovation process, is described in local languages. Attention is given first to the national projects or projects that have national partners. The EIP-AGRI database focuses on three types of projects – Operational groups, Thematic Networks and Multi-Actor Approach projects – but it also contains other innovative projects besides these ones.

Step 2: Develop a structure – navigation has to be obvious.

The database has to be efficiently searchable, using either keywords or filters. If the database consists of many project examples, the search engine must be efficient and simple. The EIP-AGRI service point updates their list of keywords annually, but the comprehensive and manageable list of keywords is a never-ending process. The frequent user of a website gains more from a clearly structured content tree.

Review the websites/databases regularly to keep up with the shift of common understanding.

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2.21. Defining a set of metadata for annotating data in a centralised repository

Collecting a number of appropriately selected resources (data objects), which have been produced by Thematic Networks, in a centralised repository is not a matter of copying and pasting files into a folder. The data need to be ‘findable’ and part of making it so is to define a set of metadata. In short terms, metadata is information about data. This information may have to do with the title and author/creator of the data object, the language in which its content is being delivered, its file format, the date of its creation, the type of the data object we are dealing with, the project from which it has been made available, and other useful information.

In order to store data into a centralised repository, we need to annotate (describe) this data by assigning values to the metadata defined. The use of metadata can significantly enhance the process of searching for data in the repository, as well as narrowing down the number of search results retrieved (after the execution of a search query) by using search filters. To address the data findability requirement, we should draw upon existing work helping to identify the most important metadata to define. Such work is made available from schema.org (<https://schema.org/>), Dublin Core (<https://dublincore.org/>), and RDF Schema (<https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>).

Details about the work done in EURAKNOS for coming up with the set of metadata required is reported in Deliverables 3.2 and 4.3.

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2.22. The visual design of online databases of innovation projects

Information visualization is important, as an average person makes a decision about the content in 10 seconds. The appearance of a database (as for every website) must be catchy and easily understandable. People's ability to read decreases with time and visualisation helps. Use a combination of the following approaches:

- Reduce the number of clicks to access the information. Choose wisely between direct posting and separate documents - uploading pdfs may be better rather than hosting the large amount of text-information directly on the webpage.
- If the message is complex for the text alone - a video, podcast or presentation may be better.
- Farmers have no time to look around in even brilliant databases. They prefer educational videos or web-based instruments without the need to download. In terms of advisers, the situation is opposite - they prefer to get the knowledge in detail.

The clear design of a database considers a content tree regarding the subject matter. Detailed search forms work only if the person knows the subject in detail. Both, national and EU level databases are needed as the needs do vary. Not all innovative projects are interesting to the farmers as they discover mainly further research needs. Simpler and easily understandable websites at national levels ensure that local information is presented. Still, the connection between EIP-AGRI database and national or local ones are expected and desired.

The websites should be tested, tested and once again tested because at the end of the day the content is the most important. If there is an essence, different tools will work.

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2.23. Language or translation of online databases

Thematic networks and innovation support services are collecting and presenting a large variety of information on their websites in several languages. There are two language issues - European languages, and appropriate use of wording.

Regarding the EU level databases, a translation is not a big issue. Advanced users of databases (like advisors, researchers, project managers etc) are familiar with the English enough and when necessary, using Google translate is in most cases sufficient to catch very first level of information. Translating everything into all the EU languages proved to be expensive and technically complicated for EIP-AGRI. Automatic translation mechanisms help to cut the project cost in terms of translation and the Chrome browser, linked to Google translator can translate every webpage to any language.

Translating the jargon or bureaucratic language cannot be done automatically. To make information maximally understandable and more practical to use, is by far the biggest challenge. There will be a never-ending need for experts to build the bridges between different stakeholders. The farmers have no time to look around in even brilliant databases; they prefer the material explained by practitioner. The translation is an important part for agricultural advisors in many elements.

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2.24. Naming conventions to follow for the documents produced by a Thematic Network

To make digital documents created by Thematic Networks available via a centralised repository, one of the challenges that needs to be addressed is that there are so many different types to consider. We may refer to factsheets, practice abstracts, newsletters, policy briefs, deliverable reports, and many more. So, how can we distinguish between all these different types of documents and collect those of interest to the repository? How can we say that a document is a practice abstract or a policy brief?

There are so many different naming conventions used by Thematic Networks that is nearly impossible to tell the type of document from the file name. This means that in order to understand the type of document, one has to read through its text to make conclusions. This is a time consuming and tedious process.

The identification of the document type can be facilitated by using the following naming convention:

- Start with the title of the document (or a short version of it).
- Include the name of the document type (e.g., practice abstract).
- Continue with the name of the Thematic Network in which the document has been produced.
- Provide the date on which the document was produced in the format YYYYMMDD.
- Use the underscore character (“_”) to denote blank spaces.
- So, the file name of a document could be, for example,
“naming_conventions_to_follow_practice_abstract_EURAKNOS_20201126.docx”

Recommendations for naming conventions are provided in Deliverable 4.3.

Character count: 1243/1500

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2.25. Knowledge reservoirs: which design for what purpose?

There are different designs for different knowledge reservoirs (KRs): While some are based on end-users' requests and needs, others are based on the type of content, which can be more or less scientific, very hands-on with lots of tips and forums, and still others are based on inputs from partners and users (videos etc...).

For the design of your KR to match its intended purpose, select which function your KR is supposed to have:

- KR as a catalogue: choose your innovation

This type of KR supports the user in their choices, oriented in the search for practical solutions. These KRs reference innovative technical solutions. Key steps for consulting content are (1) through the use of a search engine, or (2) search criteria are defined to filter solutions.

More information on the Smart-AKIS website: www.smart-akis.com

- KR as a library: find the knowledge on the right shelves

The main functionalities are a classification of contents by theme or type of content. The key steps for consulting content are guidance on the site according to a proposed thematic classification.

More information on the HNV-Link website: www.hnvlink.eu

- KR as a practical digital guide book

The main functionalities are presentation of tips and tricks as well as practical solutions. The key steps for consulting content are through the use of a search engine, and search criteria defined to filter solutions or defined on the subject on which it is focused.

More information on the SheepNet website: <http://sheepnet.network/>

- KR as a market place for sharing and exchanging good practices

This type of KR does not host any knowledge content but lists references accessible through URL links.

More information on the Skin website <http://www.shortfoodchain.eu/>

Character count: 1468/1500

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2.26. Setting up a knowledge reservoir: inventory of existing practices

A knowledge reservoir (KR) is a digital tool to disseminate knowledge on a specific area. The aim of a KR is to give access to technical outputs of Thematic Networks (TNs) that are ready for practice. All types of knowledge produced by a TN are intended to be disseminated.

To set up an effective KR in practice, you can opt to either (1) host it on a dedicated digital platform, (2) totally integrate it into the project website, or (3) adopt/choose an intermediate solution.

1) Having a dedicated knowledge platform to host the KR is not only a question of display, but it seems to be fundamental for the end users to see clearly/have clarity and find their way around.

2) Having a KR integrated into the TN project website might not provide easy visibility of the outputs available.

3) Having a mix of the two solutions, with the KR being diluted in all sections of the project website, makes it necessary to navigate through the entire website of the TN to be able to access all the knowledge content made available to the end user. It is not necessarily the most intuitive option for easy access to the most relevant content, but it can be a way to make a strong link between the TN project and the KR.

Of course, these are only the major trends because in practice the diversity of TN KRs has led to many other intermediate situations, which are all combinations of the three major trends described above.

For more information, see deliverable 2.2 from the Euraknos project:

https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/D2.2_20200216_Report_on_format_and_design_of_KRs_of_TNs.pdf

Character count: 1345/1500

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2.27. How to improve a knowledge platform: Learning from and with end users

The impact of your TN is best indicated by the uptake of best practices, methodologies, training, and educational courses by end users such as farmers, foresters, and advisors. If your TN's materials are stored on a knowledge platform, it is important to get to know its end users:

1. Assess your end users starting with defining their needs, context, expectations, motivations, and barriers.
2. Get a better understanding of how users experience the platform by using surveys, workshops, interviews, focus groups, or persona exercises.
3. Estimate the success and impact of your TN results through reflection exercises, consultations, and surveys during the project as well as a detailed evaluation afterwards.
4. Actively involve end users in the process of improving the platform.
5. Include a rating function to increase engagement and hold validation workshops to create ownership.

Measure your platform's impact with good indicators that:

- are relevant to your project and its environment, specific to the objective, easy to interpret, realistic and feasible to collect (available at an acceptable cost); and
- allow for tracking a change over a time and regularly reviewing targets, specifying quantity, quality, and time (measurable and time bound).

Qualitative indicators include user-friendly access, a search engine, and automatic profiling and translation. An example for a quantitative indicator is the number of user-friendly functionalities.

In summary, at best co-create the knowledge platform together with the future users, regularly collect feedback from end users, and use this feedback to improve the platform.

Check EURAKNOS Deliverable 2.6 and the TN Explorer's Guide for more info and indicators: <https://euraknos.eu/deliverables>

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2.28. Enhancing navigation: The example of Organic Farm Knowledge

To boost the usability and effectiveness of your project’s knowledge platform, the user interface and user experience are crucial aspects to consider, both from a technical and an end-user perspective.

- Provide search and analysis tools to enable end users to quickly find the right information.
- Labels (menu labels or page headings, for example ‘Themes’) direct users to specific areas. Make sure the labelling system is context relevant, clear, and meaningful to the users of your platform, helping them to easily determine where they are.
- Use visual semantic elements to indicate specific menu options (for example a house icon for the main page).

Have a look at the online platform Organic Farm Knowledge (<https://organic-farmknowledge.org/>) as an example of an easy-to-navigate toolbox: The homepage puts the search function and the three most important categories at the centre, allowing users to explore content within one of these categories or to search for specific content. Besides offering a clear menu navigation and the option to automatically translate content into different languages, the website is responsive to mobile devices. To know where they are on the website, end users can also use the secondary navigation tool below the page heading.

An introduction video to the platform will soon be available here: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCKA7iMg-_4SxmWbxYQzfjEw

Some more tips:

- Ensure quality control and content validation to increase the adoption and use of a platform and the knowledge and materials provided.
- Consider personalisation and/or customisation, feeding users with tailor-made content adapted to their preferences and/or offering users the flexibility to define the content they want to access.

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2.29. How to ensure long-term maintenance of a knowledge platform?

It is crucial to think about the impact of the outcomes of your Thematic Network already at the beginning of your project, during the conceptualisation phase. A digital knowledge platform can help build a self-sustaining, motivated TN community and allows actors within the network to stay connected, but you need to consider its long-term maintenance. In the case of the online platform Organic Farm Knowledge (<https://organic-farmknowledge.org/>), an Action Plan was developed to ensure the further development and long-term continuation of the platform. It outlines the management and funding model as well as the operational tasks in the areas development, coordination, and evaluation/planning. To ensure platform maintenance, focus on:

- Using the platform for learning and communication, e.g., end-user testimonies, promotion of events, publication of outputs, presentation of technical content, and references to other info sources;
- Linking to existing networks and educational initiatives from local to international level;
- Engaging local end-user groups such as Operational Groups;
- Keeping your TN website alive after the end of the project (including the regular update of linked projects);
- Keeping the network alive through social media; and
- Diversifying the sources of income, combining public and private streams (for example national governments, foundations, companies and/or end users themselves).

Before creating a new platform, consider having your project's results displayed on an existing website or database to leverage end user traffic, for example EIP-AGRI: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en>

Working with EURAKNOS & EUREKA to develop a common, EU-wide knowledge reservoir: <https://h2020eureka.eu/>

Character count: 1492/1500

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2.30. Six recommendations for improved sustainability of Thematic Networks for Agricultural and Forestry Innovation

The EURAKNOS [policy brief](#) outlines six recommendations for adapting funding programmes and frameworks to support the function and sustainability of thematic networks (TNs) and their outcomes.

1. Funding schemes should provide extra financial incentives for farmers and foresters to participate in meetings or consultation rounds to facilitate their engagement in a bottom-up approach.
2. Funding schemes should allow TNs to be flexible and responsive to challenges or changing social, economic, regulatory and environmental needs that shift or develop over the project's lifetime.
3. Funding agencies should develop and promote standardised dissemination formats, e.g. videos, presentations and infographics, which appeal to different TN target groups.
4. National, or regional and local governments should facilitate and financially support mapping of local networks and main information sources for farmers and foresters so TN outcomes can be transmitted by these trusted 'long term established networks'.
5. Funding schemes should stimulate connection to digital training to improve digital literacy and enable 'analogue users' to access online information resources and communities for peer-to-peer learning.
6. National and/or regional government departments support and fund the creation and maintenance of a common EU-wide agricultural knowledge platform where end-users can easily find information and TN outputs can be retained.

Funding and project calls should be adapted accordingly to improve interaction between actors and networks and divert budget from individual project websites to a common standardised and interoperable platform that connects to multiple actors including educational institutions.

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2.31. The basics of a branding workshop

A brand is all that is communicated visually and otherwise to portray the personality of the organisation, its products and services. And, as such, strong brands are enormously powerful business tools.

In order to infer the personality traits of the EURAKNOS project a value exercise was done during the kick-off workshop in Brussels where the involved stakeholders had to choose between several values, such as futuristic or timeless, complex or simple, customer or knowledge centric, etc. which helped the designer get a better idea of the value framework.

Subsequently, a more detailed value exercise was conducted, where the stakeholders had to imagine the organisation as a superhero with specific enemies, superpowers and a purpose, they had to choose specific images which match with the values of the organisation and explain why they chose these images by defining keywords.

Finally, the stakeholders needed to create a moodboard by selecting graphics from a predetermined selection of graphics by putting 5 green dots on the graphics they liked for the organisation and 5 red dots on graphics which they didn't like for the organisation. All of this information allowed the brand designer to subsequently draw up a proposal brand of the organisation.

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2.32. Using the knowledge exchange pathways to create higher impact

Sharing, co-creation and exchange of knowledge within a thematic network (TN) includes continuous dialogue and action between users and consortium members to allow them to influence the direction and knowledge exchange of the TN. Engaging users beyond your network is also key to creating higher impact. The Knowledge Exchange Pathways (KEP) illustrate the main mechanisms to collect, share and present your TN's ready for practice knowledge to as many users as possible.

Your TN knowledge is generated through exchange, co-learning and co-creation. This knowledge is then collected or 'harvested' for further dissemination and exploitation by Pathways 2 and 3. Pathway 2 involves multiplying the TN knowledge by network members sharing this to new/other users. Pathway 3 is another step removed and involves presenting and dispersing the knowledge to new users via various tools (recommendation: videos and podcasts) or by actors not directly involved in the network:

Collaborative processes with and by users, including peer-to-peer exchange, are the most effective strategies to help exploitation of new practices on-farm. But this is not possible for all. Utilising digital means of knowledge exchange is key. For example, bringing the knowledge creation alive for the user through videos and podcasts. Use the KEP to reflect and identify the most accessible and appropriate knowledge exchange strategies. Depending on your context, time, budget and capacity, utilising all three pathways will create higher impact. For more information, tools, practices and methods for monitoring your KEP impact please go to page 11 of the EURAKNOS Explorers Guide <https://tinyurl.com/y3pvbulv>

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2.33. Recommendations for increasing uptake of your Practice Abstract

Practice Abstracts (PAs) are a tool to disseminate knowledge generated through TNs and other Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects. They provide short and concise practical information using the EIP-AGRI common format. As part of the EURKANOS project several workshops took place with TN coordinators and end-users to provide recommendations to enhance PA uptake, use and impact.

The key recommendations were:

1. Practice abstracts must be **easily accessible** to end-users:
2. A **search function** to filter and sort on sector, topic and language is essential.
3. Many end-users across Europe do not speak English, therefore an opportunity to search on language and an option for **automatic translation** to extend the language availability.
4. End-users are interested in information on a certain topic and not interested in a specific project. All PAs should be accessible through their topic.
5. End-users need **contextual information** to understand whether the information in the PA could be applied in their context. A section to explain context should be added or the character count should be increased.
6. To support the limited character count it should be mandatory to **provide links** to videos etc. to further explore the topic.
7. Advisors help farmers to utilize information in PAs - focus on promoting PAs to **advisors** and provide support to advisors to utilise these.
8. Where permission is granted, include the **contact details** of the people that actually developed the innovation first-hand. This will increase the credibility and trustworthiness of the information.

For best practice case examples, see page 24 of the Explorers Guide https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/2020_12_01_EnglishOnlineExplorersGuide_FINAL.pdf

Character count: 1496/1500

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2.34. Practice Abstracts as a virtual bridge to further project results

Practice Abstracts (PA) are a tool to disseminate knowledge generated through TNs and other Horizon 2020 multi-actor projects to inspire and connect actors across the EU. They provide short and concise practical information using the EIP-AGRI common format.

In the EURKANOS project several workshops took place with TN coordinators and end-users to discuss how to utilise PAs as a virtual bridge to further project results.

One of the main conclusions was to keep the limited character count defined in the common format, where PAs should act as virtual bridge to further information.

Furthermore, the following recommendations were made to make the most of your PAs:

- Promote your PAs through your project communications during the lifetime of your project, e.g. newsletter, twitter and other social media.
- Use PAs for cross-exchange and sharing with end-users directly involved in your project countries. The short format can easily be translated and provides a ‘teaser’ to generate further interest in project results.
- Engage end-users in the development of the PAs to create user friendly outputs, for example discuss with them which project outputs they find most useful to share.
- Use links in your PA to maximise additional project outputs such as factsheets, technical notes or videos. In several TN PAs are effectively linked to more elaborate fact sheets or technical notes.
- Explore options for the end-users involved in your project to promote the practice abstract themselves through their own communication channels and social media networks.

For best practice case examples, see page 24 of the Explorers Guide

https://euraknos.fra1.digitaloceanspaces.com/production/deliverables/2020_12_01_EnglishOnlineExplorersGuide_FINAL.pdf

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2.35. Ten rules for virtual demonstration

A "virtual demonstration" (VD) (or "farminar") is an online event aiming to present an innovation in an agricultural context. Virtual demonstration "rules" have been defined in the Nefertiti project (<https://nefertiti-h2020.eu/>) and completed by other experiences on demonstration. Rules could be found on <https://trainingkit.farmdemo.eu/demo-design-guide-for-virtual-demonstrations/>.

1. First, objectives of the VD need to be clear: Why do you want to organise the demo? Who do you target? What do you want to demonstrate?
2. The topic should comply with farmers' immediate concerns, and include information on economic and production impacts
3. A good internet connection is needed for operating a specialised platform (ie Microsoft Teams, Go To Meeting, Skype, Zoom, Jitsi Meeting, ...)
4. The ideal number of participants depends on the objective: large number of participants for informing widely with little interaction, or a small group to discuss a topic, co-create and foster knowledge exchange and peer to peer learning.
5. The length of virtual demonstration should not exceed 90 minutes in order to keep participants interested and include sufficient time for interaction.
6. The demo should use material referring to on-farm practice, such as videos, pictures, farmer testimonies, presentation of practical research results, live streaming, virtual reality....
7. Targeted public will be informed through mailings, websites, social media, radio announcements, newspapers...
8. A facilitator and a demonstrator are needed. The facilitator will animate the session and operate the platform.
9. The demonstrator is the expert/farmer who gives a presentation or testimony, explains a video and stays focused on the content. Interaction with the participants will be stimulated (Q&A session, chat, quiz, survey, brainstorming and pin boards...) (example on : https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kjJe4_UE9zY).
10. Finally, evaluate your VD by collecting participants' feedback. Furthermore, additional documentation or recording of the VD can be provided.

Character count: 1479/1500

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2.36. Cross Exchange Visit in virtual mode

The physical Cross Exchange Visit method (see AgriSpin Deliverable 2.4 <https://agrispin.eu/>) aims at sharing information about practices/instruments used by farms. Generally, mixed teams visit an object during 3-5 consecutive days and have informal interactions between colleagues from different corners of Europe. A digital cross-exchange is less time-consuming for participants (only a couple of hours), but the end-users are less engaged and continuous contacts afterwards seldom happen. For active discussion within a limited time, the methodology has to be revised.

Step 1: Prepare yourself.

- Keep the title, aim and agenda of cross exchange clear. Select tools, which are comfortable to use, for both host and participants.
- Pick the presenters that have a previous understanding of state of play and people involved. Ask to provide presentations before the event and make them available in various back-up modes.
- Prepare structure for the participants and select certain ones who have an opinion about the matters in order to encourage discussion.

Step 2: Get organised.

- Select a location with stable and fast internet connection, and keep an IT specialist close by.
- The kick-off has to be brief: prepare the participants beforehand, give them specific tasks and make an agreement with those, who you expect to contribute.
- Let the participants discuss and direct the questions to your desired path. Follow the agenda regarding preannounced subthemes.
- Reflections on the presented cases have to happen during the event, ask for the reflections both orally and in writing.

Step 3: Follow-up and feedback.

- Make a full memo of the performed event. Thereto, send out follow-up survey but do not expect many responses.

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2.37. How to better engage end-users in online meetings and webinars

Many actors are very busy, so it is important to structure topics clearly and organise them well so that actors can assess the effort and get a real benefit from an event.

Step 1: Prepare an efficient promotion campaign

- Organise an efficient promotion campaign about the online meeting well in advance
- Point out strategic communication channels to be used for the promotion purpose
- Launch the promotion campaign on multi-channels at the same time (for example on social media, flyers, posters, project's website) and keep it active until the online meeting day.

Step 2: Prepare yourself

- Prepare a simple and clear agenda for the online meeting
- Ensure that the topics selected for discussion sessions are in line with end-users' skills and expectations
- Prepare an attractive support of presentation you can use while facilitating the online meeting

Step 3: Follow-up and feedback

- Take written notes of the performed online meeting.
- Send out follow-up surveys to all attendees and collect feedback
- Use feedback in order to continuously improve the quality of webinars and participants' satisfaction

Character Count: 934/1500

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2.38. How to communicate efficiently about TN outputs and results in end-user's demonstration days

Communication with the end users is very much shaped by the communication channels. It has been found that diversity is crucial in reaching end-users, as everyone has and uses their favourite communication channel. For example, younger people may prefer social media channels, or older people may prefer newspapers or fax machines. It should therefore always be considered which target group should be chosen.

Step 1: Be direct and concise

- Make sure you convey one key message
- Make sure that this one message is clearly understood by your audience
- Give your audience time for questions

Step 2: Clearly show the relevance of the results presented (focus on how the project results can help end users solve their problem)

- Use facts and figures in attractive formats
- Repeat the message
- Summarise the most important results at the end of the presentation day

Step 3: Follow-up and feedback

- Collect feedback on the demonstration days
- Use the feedback to continuously improve the quality of your demonstration days

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2.39. How to organize online meetings which strengthen synergies between different TNs and OGs

Step 1: identify the type of synergies you wish to create and/or strengthen with other related thematic networks and/or operational groups

Point out critical topics/challenges your thematic network is dealing with

Prepare a series of subtopics for cross-cutting discussions within TN community and OGs

Ask yourself: ‚what would be the added-value to share this meeting with such and such TN/OG?‘ and use your answer to motivate your invitations to be sent to the TN community and OGs

Step2: activate/re-activate strategic contacts

Use your existing network and contacts in order to get a quick overview of current thematic networks and/or operational groups active on related topics

Subscribe to EURAKNOS newsletters [EURAKNOS Newsletter - March \(EN\) \(campaign-archive.com\)](https://campaign-archive.com) in order to receive monthly the very last updates on thematic networks and/or operational groups

Focus on the added-value that the other TNs/OGs you wish to involve will experience by joining your online meeting

Step 3: Follow-up and feedback

Collect feedback about your online meeting

Use feedback in order to continuously improve the quality of your online meetings

Character count: 968/1500

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2.40. How to better promote end-user surveys using webinars

Step 1: Set your end-user survey

- Set your end-user survey in a digital format (for example using the tool SurveyMonkey)
- Go for a short survey with a limited number of questions
- Go for a simple and quick way to collect answers, ideally with automatic saves and results summary automatically generated (for example through SurveyMonkey or Mentimeter)
- Set a timeframe (for example one week) in which the end-user survey remains accessible and active

Step 2: Promote your end-user survey during the webinar efficiently

- Prepare a dedicated slide on the PowerPoint presentation which serves to support your webinar
- The dedicated slide will highlight the Hyperlink to the end-user survey
- Avoid too much text on the slide
- Make it visual and attractive

Step 3: Follow-up and feedback

- Send out reminders about your end-user survey and about the timeframe in which it is technically possible to participate (for example per email to all attendees of your meeting)
- Ask for feedback on your survey
- Use feedback in order to continuously improve the quality of your end-users surveys

Character count: 908/1500

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2.41. Relevant dissemination from Thematic Networks (TNs)

Disseminating information relevant to the target group is essential within TNs and thus within EURAKNOS. This is necessary for several reasons: It places the project in the spotlight, helps to find local actors and stakeholders and convinces them of the importance of the project, thus contributing to a social, environmental, economic or policy impact.

Relevant dissemination depends on several factors:

- The topic
- The target groups
- Geography
- The message

Example:

Within SuWaNu's thematic network, the best examples are collected regarding the use of reclaimed water for irrigation purposes. Several research projects can be very interesting and relevant for the regions in which this TN operates.

A project in the Netherlands where polluted wastewater from breweries is reused as water for irrigation of agricultural crops is particularly relevant for Belgium with all its breweries. A Spanish research project where recovered water is used to irrigate olive trees is irrelevant in a country without olive trees.

In addition to the topic that has to match the geography, it also has to be a good match with the target group and the message. Find out which target group fits perfectly with a particular research project within a TN and how best to reach them. Finally, pay attention to the message. Don't hold a promo talk for the project. Tell the target group how they can benefit from it.

Character count: 1172 /1500

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2.42. The ambassador: a key person in the dissemination of knowledge

A key step for a Thematic Network (TN) to generate high impact is to succeed in the dissemination of knowledge so that farmers, foresters and advisers know, use and spread this knowledge. It is likely that your TN will encounter the challenge that farmers often need time to process and adapt a new practice on their farms. User ambassadors from within the TN as intermediary knowledge brokers can provide spaces to facilitate this transfer of relevant TN knowledge into practice. These ambassadors or influencers from within the network have potential to share the knowledge so that it reaches new users.

Farmers trust other farmers and are a public for which oral communication and knowledge exchange remains highly important. Thus, they are very keen on peer-to-peer learning. When a farmer shares an innovation with another farmer, the message has much more impact.

Therefore, consider making use of the following exploitation mechanisms, based on experience from previous and existing TN activities:

- Use flagship ambassadors to reach end users and give visibility and credibility to the knowledge exchange outputs.
- Leverage existing farmer groups, monitor farms or discussion forums to share knowledge with new end users.
- Use existing farmer networks of influencers as well as established and trusted means of communication to end users, working with existing exploitation infrastructures.
- Harness existing transnational and national workshops, events, conferences and industry demonstration events, and international exchange visits for advisors.
- To increase engagement with new end users, include a rating function of the knowledge exchange activity or output.
- Work together with other projects and synergise exploitation activities.

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2.43. Newsletters that generate impact for a TN

A newsletter is the perfect tool to keep everyone informed about the activities of a TN. At least if this is done in the right way. In order to generate impact, Euraknos also took a number of parameters into account:

- Determine objectives and work towards it. Do you just want to inform or do you want people to click through to a site?
- Determine your target group. A policy maker wants different information than a grower. You can choose to make different versions of a newsletter.
- Choose a unique design and keep the texts short and powerful. Lift a tip of the veil and ensure a good call to action to your website.
- Write strong titles. Both in the newsletter and in the subject line of the mail. Strong, engaging titles make readers willing to read further and click on links.
- Give your newsletter a face. Readers want to know that there are people behind the project and the newsletter. Moreover, make sure you have unique content. Readers are subscribed to a newsletter to be the first to receive unique information. Deliver them what they want.
- Make sure the timing is impeccable. Regularly check the statistics of your newsletters and find out what works when and for whom.

Newsletters are not an exact science. There is no golden formula, not even for the number of newsletters. Adapt the number of newsletters to your content. Better a newsletter less than a newsletter without content.

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2.44. How to interpret data from newsletters

Newsletters create a lot of impact within a TN. A newsletter is the ideal way to inform a large target group about new initiatives and everything that is going on in a short period of time. About a week after sending your newsletter you can start interpreting the data, because measuring is knowing. The results of a newsletter consist of three things:

1. The delivery ratio

In other words, how many people have your mail in their inbox? And how many bounces do you have? For example: $(100 \text{ sent} - 2 \text{ bounces}) / 100 = \text{A delivery rate of } 98\%$.

2% of the mails that 'bounces' is completely normal. This is a qualitative mail. If the percentage is higher, then something is wrong with the quality of your email addresses or your ESP (Email Service Provider).

2. The open ratio

This is the percentage of unique recipients who have opened your newsletter and it says something about the quality of your subject line and popularity of the sender.

For example: $\text{opened mails } 40 / 100 \text{ delivered mails} = \text{an open ratio of } 40\%$.

Anything above 30% is a good open ratio.

3. The click-to-open ratio

This is the percentage that clicked on a link in your newsletter. Only count the unique clicks.

For example: $\text{Clicked on a link in newsletter } 20 / 40 \text{ opened mails} = \text{CTO of } 50\%$.

The better the quality of the mail, the higher your CTO. A higher CTO can be reached by using multiple links in your newsletter, creating clear call to actions and a clear layout.

Character count: 1175/1500

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2.45. More engagement on LinkedIn with your Thematic Network

"You never get a second chance to make a first impression"

Do you want engagement on your LinkedIn page? Present your TN as an expert in its field. LinkedIn is a very valuable channel for this. Here are a few points of attention to make it successful.

1. Make sure your TN profile is up to date and reflects the expertise you aim for.
2. Make sure to create good content. Good content shared by employees/partners creates a snowball effect in a short period of time. The more interaction in a short period of time, the bigger the chance of high engagement. A LinkedIn page is not only made for advertising. Put your qualities or expertise as a TN in the spotlight, tell how you can add value but also focus on the human aspect. Let your people speak. Relevant hashtags and tags ensure further distribution and engagement of your posts. Just like a 'call to action' often triggers a reaction.
3. Ensure regularity. You can only stay top of mind and provoke engagement if you continue to produce content. Create a good strategy and team to meet all expectations.
4. Share content from other partners with additional expertise or initiatives with similar interfaces. React regularly with a simple emoji or reply to other posts. Communication is a dialogue, not a monologue. In the frame of EURAKNOS it is interesting to take this into account as the essence of a thematic network is to transfer knowledge.

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2.46. Engaging content for a successful podcast

Podcasts are quickly becoming one of the most common methods to consume content. They can be listened to at any point in everyday life, e.g. when exercising, cooking, or during the commute to work. But in this new world of millions of podcasts which cover every topic imaginable, how can you ensure your podcast stands out and gets the attention it deserves?

EURAKNOS set out to release 50 podcasts across the duration of our project. The aim of the podcast series is to communicate about our plans, progress, and key outputs, and to promote the work of other Thematic Networks within our network. So how do we ensure our podcasts make for good listening?

Firstly, we suggest avoiding the use of acronyms and jargon as they can alienate the listener who is likely to be external to your project (and EU H2020 projects in general). Use simple, easily understood terms to help listeners to understand the topic of your discussion. We advise that your podcast uses relaxed, light-hearted conversation. Avoid scripting as this can make the podcast sound rigid. Try to focus on different angles when discussing your chosen topic. How does your subject branch out into other areas and contexts, and how does this then link back to the project? We recommend considering how your topic could fit with current affairs and news. By associating the podcast with topics featured in the news, you can generate more interest by linking to current, relevant issues and this will be useful when promoting the podcast. Finally, keep your podcast short and engaging, consider your own attention span and interests and apply it to your podcast.

For a good example of a fluid, well implemented podcast, check out ‘Workshop facilitation - Handy advice from a social psychologist – EURAKNOS podcast’ on [Spotify](#).

Character count: 1490/1500

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2.47. Creating and editing a successful podcast

EURAKNOS set a target of 50 podcasts to be released over the course of the project. To make the most of existing contacts, all project partners have played a role in recording material for the EURAKNOS podcasts, most of whom have no prior experience. This abstract explains how simple it is to create podcasts.

Specialist recording equipment is available, but we suggest simply recording the podcast using a smart phone or Dictaphone placed centrally to all members of the conversation. However, it has not been possible to do this through the COVID-19 pandemic. Instead, we used the recording function available through online meeting software like ‘Microsoft Teams’ or ‘Zoom’ to carry out interviews. This simple facility has allowed the continuation of podcast recording in 2020 when face-to-face meetings were not possible. This option has been extremely effective and might be considered as a method to create podcasts with limited budget, even once physical meetings are permitted.

The next step is to edit the podcast. We suggest using audio or video editing software such as Audacity, Adobe Premier Pro or Apple iMovie. There are many programmes available with plenty of tutorial videos available on YouTube to help guide the editing process.

Short intro and outro music should be used to help make the podcast sound more professional and we advise using the same music for each individual episode in the series for consistency, similar to a theme tune. You can also record acknowledgements to feature at the end of each episode, for example our EU funding declaration and credit for music.

For more details on how to edit and create podcasts, listen to the EURAKNOS podcast: ‘EURAKNOS – communicating through videos & podcasts’, available on [Spotify](#).

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2.48. How to produce more impactful videos targeting farmers, foresters and advisers

The new media and the fact that the equipment of people through cell phones, laptops, tablets, etc. has improved continuously in recent years, has developed its own way of communicating. The videos, are now used not only for information exchange but also for marketing, self-promotion or sales. The medium of video messages is fast, simple and convincing. The thematic networks must focus the medium even more to reach the end-users in the future.

Translated with www.DeepL.com/Translator (free version)

Step1: The Storytelling

Prepare a good story to increase interest in the video

Make the storytelling as short as possible

Make the storytelling accessible by using appropriate languages to better reach your audience

Step 2: Choosing the protagonists

The protagonists you select should be the best possible communicators available at the time

The protagonists must be convincing

The protagonists are ideal contacts for future collaboration on educational/educational videos

Step 3: Follow-up and feedback

Collect feedback on the video

Use the feedback to continuously improve the quality of your videos

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2.49. The TN Explorer's Guide: flagship product of the EURAKNOS project

The TN Explorer's Guide provides a support framework to learn from previous Thematic Network (TN) projects, to reflect, and to implement the most relevant elements in order to create the highest possible impact.

To boost the success of your TN, here are some clues: the guide starts at the conceptualisation stage, considering ways to incorporate the multi-actor approach (MAA) into a consortium and project design.

The MAA is all about bringing together people with unique, complementary skills from science and practice, to co-create knowledge that can be readily applied by end users.

User engagement and knowledge exchange are key to a successful TN project. The Knowledge Exchange Pathways concept illustrates the main mechanisms to collect, co-create and share TN's ready-for-practice knowledge.

It is important to agree on how to work together and function effectively as a MA consortium in order to achieve the project objectives. Using a facilitator to support the consortium in working cohesively, and effectively engaging with users can be hugely beneficial.

You can also use participatory needs assessments to further shape and develop the project's theme. Involve farmers, foresters and advisors as key knowledge providers to select good practices that can inspire or be applied by others in order to optimise their agricultural or forestry practice.

The next step is to share and disseminate these good practices beyond your network, many ways to do this! Active involvement of users is vital for sustaining the valuable results and networks beyond the lifespan of the project itself.

Check out the TN Explorer's Guide, available through the EURAKNOS website and see the promotion video <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xxV1YFADA7I>

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2.50.Improving the structural organization of the TNs towards more efficient C&D

- All TNs are communicating and disseminating allowing the project to generate some impact.
- However, the impact is not as successful as expected. Even with elaborated C&D plans, the activities are time-consuming for a low vision of end-user engagement and uptake of results.
- C&D appears as a constraint for TN partners, and the partner responsible must find some motivational strategies to involve people. Efficiency should be more stimulated and can be improved by internal communication and by sharing projects and network solutions, strategies, and tools.
- Languages and translations remain the main barrier to C&D activities. TNs are trying to translate at the maximum but it usually comes to a lack of resources in terms of budget and time.

Best practices to be adopted:

- Future calls on EU TNs should mention that dissemination of projects results should be as important as the collection, adaptation, and translation of knowledge
- Consortia must allocate more budget and personal time to C&D.
- All partners should be committed to these activities from the very beginning of the project and be aware that it's the most important task of the project instead of a constraint.
- Internal communication and efficient partner management is key to better stimulate project partners for dissemination activities;
- Considering the language barrier for knowledge sharing and innovation uptake, national and regional C&D plans must be foreseen to directly reach the target with the project outputs.

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2.51. Enhancing the impact of TNs through professional communication skills and partners

- Even if the TNs aim to disseminate technical knowledge to end-users, partners are not often professionals of C&D.
- The distinction between C&D is not that simple: even if the strategy differs, it ends most of the time with common practice for both activities. Although messages, materials, channels and tools are separated according to target groups and TN objectives, it is challenging to apply it in practice, mostly because of the identification of end-user and the key messages to address.
- Even if the TNs made their best to be as accurate as possible in the production of outcomes, end-user languages remain an important barrier to properly reach the expected targets with the relevant tools.
- There is currently no effective tool to measure impact, and TNs are wondering how to evaluate their practices and how can it be adapted in the future.

Best practices to be adopted:

- Future TNs should recruit professional communication and dissemination partners for C&D activities that will considerably help TNs to improve them on the following aspects:
 - the distinction between C&D, clear and professional C&D strategy;
 - better use and adaptation of C&D channels and tools with regards to the targets;
 - adaptation of the material to the right language for the right targets;
 - better management of the project partners for C&D activities and to adapt their strategy to their national and regional area;
 - use of the professional tools for measurement of the C&D activities and their impacts.

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2.52. Using the right channels & tools for the right target audience

- The identification of the audience may not be restricted to the type of actors, but also their common practices, age, and preference in terms of the channel.
- There is a need for decision making support tools on how to select a blend of multiple channels and a portfolio of tools/materials that will lead to high impact communication to the specific audiences.
- The access to ready to use technical and practical material for end-users on the project websites must be improved. The constitution of easy to identify and to access repositories of end-user material must be a priority for future TNs and all EU Research and Innovation projects.
- C&D activities should be organized in a complementary way to efficiently reach both objectives.
- The Farm Demo projects³ stated the recommendation below that must be followed for more efficient dissemination to practitioners: “On-farm demonstration – in the case it brings benefits (which are understood as such) to end-users/farmers - should be an essential part of the dissemination activities of EIP AGRI projects, TNs, OGs and other European project programs such as Horizon Europe and Interreg, in particular when aiming at innovation”. (EU SCAR AKIS (2019), Preparing for Future AKIS in Europe. Brussels, EC).

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³ AgriDemo F2F : <https://farmdemo.eu>

PLAID : <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/peer-peer-learningaccessing-innovation-through>

NEFERTITI : <https://nefertiti-h2020.eu>

2.53. Maximizing the Impact of C&D activities

- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are outlined during the setting up phase of the project and presented in the impact section. However, they are rarely or at least not systematically mentioned in C&D Plans and linked to the C&D channels of the project.
- There's a wide range of tools to monitor and assess the activity of C&D channels. Even if these tools are broadly used by the TNs for quantitative analysis, we notice a lack of monitoring outreach of the TNs through qualitative analysis.
- The main aim of TNs is to disseminate to end-users and ready to use techniques and best practices in agriculture. However, we notice a lack of impact 'culture' within the community composing most of the TNs.

Position to be adopted:

- TNs must systematically and carefully link the KPIs mentioned in the proposal to their C&D plan. This action will provide efficient monitoring tools for C&D activities throughout the project.
- TNs should not only use quantitative tools, but also a set of tools allowing to measure the qualitative impact of their activities. Surveys and interviews toward the targeted end-user community should be performed along the project to evaluate the knowledge produced.
- TNs which aim to deliver operational solutions to end-users, must improve their impact culture straight from the beginning of the project. This impact culture must be taught and pushed by the coordinator and the responsible partner for C&D so that all partners are more committed to efficient C&D activities.

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2.54. What is needed for successful adaptation of good practices?

TNs accumulate valuable knowledge on innovative practices. This knowledge is usually made available in an online knowledge reservoir (KR). Experiences have shown that some preconditions are needed for KRs to become functional. Preconditions are content, and methodology related.

Content related preconditions:

- Detailed information about legal background is needed in addition to summary, especially for decision makers to promote development.
- Besides scientifically detailed information also basic economical calculations are needed, especially for advisors and hubs to prove economical return to farmers.
- If a case study with detailed legal and economic information is not available, a solution can be to give the contact details of a competent contact organisation/person who can be asked about details.
- To get in touch with someone who has implemented the innovation is useful for farmers in case of being stuck. Chat function can ensure a lively connection.

Methodology related preconditions:

- Attention of end users should be drawn to the fact that good practices adaptation must start with an internal inventory (SWOT analyses), followed by market-, and cost-benefit analyses. An innovation hub can help to do this.
- As adaptation of innovation is an experimental learning process regular follow up is essential for efficiency. Depending on capacities, innovation hubs should play a role in the process.

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2.55. Main support and tools after the project?

A cooperative network with measurable results is not only the baseline but also the sustainability pledge of TNs work, which play an important role in the European innovation ecosystem. In general, TN networks will remain active if their members acknowledge that their invested effort will return.

Economical driving force of TN network can be supported by:

- national policy commitment
- having an innovation broker/coordinator at national level (multiple roles)
- keeping up continuous liaison
- finding synergies to connect
- well defined, scalable exploitation and development objectives
- follow-up of results and incorporate experiences
- ensuring transparency

National coordinator is a multiple role with a high demand on systems approach, professional and communication skills. It is hardly manageable as a side job.

Contact tool can be:

- regular working group
- sample farm
- related projects, trainings, workshops, conferences
- briefings, newsletters, social media presence
- open source knowledge reservoir
- needs assessment and evaluation (questionnaire, interview, case studies)

Although networking is a multifunctional tool to catalyse knowledge transfer, practice-based innovation and lobbying at the same time, development of national network is slow in countries with no strong tradition on self-organisation. It can be accelerated by finding the right synergies on different levels which is based on a deep understanding of needs.

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2.56. Successful online meetings with end users start with good preparation!

Online meetings bring end users together in a time- and cost-efficient way, making it possible for a broad audience around the world to take part as well as to reach and inspire new actors to trial, innovate, and apply their own practical solutions to context-specific problems. Farmers mainly take up information from people and channels they trust. This makes collaborative processes with and by end users the most effective strategy for sharing the solutions created by your TN, implementing new practices, and facilitating communication and coordination between local to European levels. The Covid-19 crisis has put additional emphasis on the need for people to meet online.

For an optimal virtual experience:

- Choose the right software.
 - High-quality video and features such as built-in surveys, polls, live chat, and live streaming make your meeting more interactive and engaging, while also adding a personal touch.
 - Include networking possibilities such as informal “meet and greet” sessions, inviting participants to connect over a tea or coffee.
- ask the participants for their consent to record and share the meeting and engage users beyond your network, for instance by linking the meeting to other topic-related projects to increase the impact and spread innovative practices across borders.
- Use a variety of channels for the promotion, including email invitations, social media, websites, newsletters, as well as partners’ local and well-established networks and channels.
- Keep the webinar succinct (45 min - 1h), scheduled to suit multiple time zones.

Overview of tools: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Comparison_of_web_conferencing_software

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2.57. Online meetings with end users: Using GoToTraining as a tool

The interactive online training software GoToTraining (<https://www.gotomeeting.com/en-gb/training>) can be a useful and effective tool for learning and knowledge exchange with end users, in particular farmers and foresters. There are 3 options: Starter, Pro, and Plus, ranging from 107-315€ and 25-200 participants and including different functions such as break-out collaboration. Watch the tutorial for managing activities and break-outs: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8NADujLu6f0>

Attendees can join a training via browser or download the app.

The most important features include:

- A chat to exchange messages and ask questions to the speakers/trainers as an easy way of communication;
- Tests to recall/evaluate knowledge before, during and after a session;
- Polls to get immediate feedback; and
- A library to organise and store content such as training materials, tests and recordings.

Some practical tips:

- Make sure to upload and set up all materials, activities for break-outs and polls you want to organise, store and share in the library beforehand.
- Test the tool well in advance to become familiar with it.
- Let the participants know you are recording the event and share the recording afterwards.
- Ensure good facilitation.
- Clearly instruct the attendees how they can join the event. Provide the Training ID by email, ideally in the form of a calendar invitation.
- Tell the participants to use hand raising or write in the chat to signal that they want to ask a question. The chat can be more efficient than letting everyone speak.
- As presenter, you can see who has access to which functions. If needed, you can mute/unmute all participants and change the presenter to let someone else speak and share their screen.

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2.58. End-user engagement in operational groups and innovative projects

To boost innovation in agriculture and forestry, multi-actor projects must significantly impact end-users. It is not always easy to reach or engage them. This was an interesting point of discussion during the cross-exchange visit on the topic of smart protection organised within the EURAKNOS framework.

One crucial aspect for end-user engagement, is to stimulate and foster interactions between actors. To implement this, peer-to-peer learning is fundamental. Farmers need to be put in the environment to work with other farmers that are willing to demonstrate technical solutions. This can be done by creating hubs of farms and demo events, which will allow farmers who are not in the network to be involved in demonstration activities. This is the case of OG “Smart spraying on Olive Trees”. In fact, in Greece farms are grouped in “cooperatives” that act as role models. If they adopt new technologies or practices the others will follow by themselves, creating an easy environment to disseminate.

Fundamentally, farmers are not the only ones that can benefit from peer-to-peer knowledge exchange. In fact, this happens also between advisors and facilitators through training and sector meetings. They need to build specific skills for coaching and fostering the knowledge exchange among actors. In fact, technical skills are not enough to create an enabling environment. This was also demonstrated during workshops organized by the EURAKNOS project, where the “ideal” skills that a facilitator should have were defined. One of many is to be able to interact with several groups of people by creating an appropriate space that allows the creation of trust among end-users, who will then be more inclined to actively participate in a project.

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2.59. How to plan a successful consortium meeting

It all starts with the location. Not only with the choice of the city and a place that is easily accessible for all the consortium members, but also with the selection of a good venue. This, together with a clear objective of the meeting, helps to set the scene for a successful event.

Our main advice is to make the meetings interactive with some moments of ‘fun’. We tried to limit presentations with only one speaker and mix those with small workshops or exercises. For example, at the kick-off meeting, we organized a human bingo as a get-to-know each other exercise. It is important to create a good foundation and motivate partners to work together towards a common goal. This can be achieved thanks to brainstorming sessions between presentations and idea sessions with post-it notes. Another trick is to make sure everyone is standing up during these interactive moments. For example, people had to move to the right or the left of the room depending on their opinion about certain discussion topics. To engage everyone, a good facilitator is very important.

One last recommendation is that the meeting should have the right duration. The ideal format that we experienced is to organize a consortium meeting over two days where people have the opportunity to fly in or travel in the morning and leave the second day in the afternoon. This way people have to book one overnight stay and in the evening they have the opportunity to visit the location that is hosting the meeting and to get to know the other consortium members.

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2.60. Mobilising networks to optimise health, energy and function

In a virtual EURAKNOS cross exchange, Dr Eelke Wielinga, shared insights into how networkers can mobilise to optimise health, energy and function of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS). Two key recommendations were shared:

1. The quality of an innovation system depends on the quality of its wiring. Networking is therefore key. In order to achieve this, space (trust), equity and free actors are required to build and maintain connections.
2. Innovation networks cannot be managed, but professional guidance can make the difference. This requires, a good biotope for Free Actors, Reflection on processes, and peer-to-peer consultations.

Networking is a multi-actor process as knowledge emerges from the interaction between different network members. Networks are also a co-creative process, where innovation is a collective discover journey.

The full webinar is available here <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9o-OVgv6Apl>

So how do we mobilise networks?

Human networks are living organisms where the health of the network depends on the quality of the connections (or the wiring). Dr Wielinga recommends you focus on the energy of the network, recognising where you and other networkers are on the innovation discovery journey, and acting accordingly. Here, a healthy network is therefore responsive to energy changes, and capable of finding answers to new emerging agricultural challenges (innovating).

The Spiral of Innovations (initiatives) sets out the seven energising phases a network moves through in order to progress from an early idea to fully embedding the innovation in agriculture. For more information on Energising Networks and tools for co-creation, please go to Netwerk&Co <https://www.netwerkenco.nl/english/>

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2.61. Facilitating Farmer Led Innovation

In a recent virtual EURAKNOS cross exchange, Russ Carrington, shared insights on how knowledge exchange and innovation among Pasture Fed Livestock Association's 600 strong membership was facilitated. Russ was joined by Kate Still (Farming Programme Delivery Manager at Soil Association), Dr Lisa Morgans (Head of Precision Livestock at Innovation for Agriculture) and Dr Jessica Stokes (Hennovation facilitator) who also shared key tips:

- Use online forums to compliment facilitation in the field, reinforcing a culture which fosters an inclusive community of practice, building trust and enabling collaborative knowledge exchange.
- The facilitators are the antenna of the group, to continually assess, monitor and reflect on where the community are on their innovation journey; being flexible and adaptive to changing needs, energy and aspirations.
- Farmer led innovation is for all farmers, but different groups of farmers will be at different stages on the innovation journey – the facilitator is to recognise this and respond accordingly, i.e. introducing external resource, knowledge or inspiration.

The interactive session highlighted new opportunities that have emerged for facilitating farmer led innovation (in the era of COVID), such as:

- The rise of virtual interactive farm tours, zoom webinars and flipped labs/classrooms
- The emerging use of WhatsApp and podcasts to create communities of practice and share farmer led innovation

The full webinar is available here <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=QBgazDw-ba0> along with a podcast on facilitating farmer led innovation to address multiple societal challenges, such as ecological breakdown, climate change and Brexit

<https://open.spotify.com/episode/4RF5BHgMohSwYjSCRpeF0w>

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2.62. Hosting online meetings with end users: How to ensure a smooth running

Online meetings are an increasingly common and appealing way to interact and engage with end users, due to the need for homeworking in the current Covid-19 pandemic and the time and costs saved by not having to travel to physical meetings. They allow you to reach a worldwide audience and to invite guest speakers. Even people who are not used to speaking up or raise questions in public may join the discussion.

To ensure a smooth running, clarity, and a real benefit:

- Make all relevant info available well in advance, including presentations and materials such as polls that need to be uploaded beforehand.
- Information on process design, expectations, roles and responsibilities, actions, and timings must be even more deliberate, accurate, and actionable than in face-to-face meetings.
- Use interactive features such as a live chat to enable and stimulate discussion and the exchange of knowledge and experiences, engaging the participants and allowing them to ask each other for help, get advice and acquire new knowledge, share best practices and solutions, network and build communities of interest.
- Ensure good facilitation to guide this knowledge exchange.
- If there is not enough time for questions during the meeting, extract all questions in the chat and let the speakers provide answers afterwards.
- Include this written Q&A in the follow-up email to all participants, together with links to the recordings and presentations, other background info and a short feedback survey to improve your next meeting.

Ultimately, reflection and learning will generate collective knowledge that can be applied to future events.

Also check out this Slack guide to remote meetings: <https://slack.com/intl/en-be/blog/collaboration/ultimate-guide-remote-meetings>

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2.63. Organising online meetings with end users: Accounting for end-user needs

Online meetings as a time- and cost-saving way to inform and interact with farmers, advisors and other end users require good organisation and planning:

- Invite the participants via email and/or newsletter as direct and effective communication channels. You can also use a combination of channels, including social media and magazines.
- Find complementary, diverse, and new topics that are relevant for practitioners.
- Ensure good moderation/facilitation and preparation of speakers in advance. Minimise the waiting time before the start of the meeting.
- Ensure good visuals to compensate for the language barrier. If possible, provide translation options, for example Zoom has a language interpretation feature: <https://blog.zoom.us/host-multilingual-events-live-language-interpretation/>). There are different service providers specialised on remote simultaneous interpretation.
- Provide possibilities to interact. For example, use Slido (<https://www.sli.do/features-live-qa>) to host Q&A sessions and live polls. Enrich the exchange by encouraging everyone to ask for clarifications and to express their views.
- Account for different levels of experience with digital applications. A small group and frequently used tools that run on smartphones such as WhatsApp might better engage farmers, especially older farmers that are not used to online tools.. If possible, provide training/support to increase their digital literacy.
- To record and share the webinar, send a consent form to the participants in advance, making sure that they cannot see each other's email address to comply with GDPR.
- Collect feedback, for example through a short follow-up survey or an informal chat with the participants, to improve future meetings.

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2.64. How to prepare for networking online as organizer

Some find online contact easier compared to physical contact, whereas for others the screen can be a barrier. The fact that almost everything is recorded, when attending online events, can be a constraint for participants either, in terms of making mistakes or perhaps that participants are limiting themselves in expressing their opinions. Also, often, online events are very formal. Thus, the challenge is to create a kind of trust and to create a more informal environment outside of the presentations where the focus is on forming the framework for the warm processes to take place.

At physical meetings and events, networking is what happens outside of the meeting room. It takes place after a presentation, during the coffee break, at the lunch or dinner table, in the evening if you go out etc. As an organizer of online meetings, you need to think of how to create a similar atmosphere when being together online. Some ideas on how to do this are listed below:

- Let the participants get the opportunity to meet each other informally before the real meeting starts;
- Create breakout rooms with smaller groups, which can be entered before the meeting, during breaks and after the meeting. The set-up can be informal but also of more formal kind e.g.; encourage participants to use the chat function to get in contact with each other and to meet in breakout rooms.

In order to facilitate a more informal environment there are some digital tools or features that you can use during the meeting:

- A survey tool where responses from participants are shown directly on the screen;
- A board tool where hosts and participants can display their thoughts;
- Encourage participants to use the chat and the webcam when possible.

There are many digital tools and features – go out and explore.

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2.65. How to perform networking online as participants

At times when physical meetings and conferences are not possible, we have only the opportunity to meet online. It is different compared to meeting in real life and possibly, you miss the face-to-face conversation with other participants outside of the formal event at coffee breaks or after the event. However, participating in online meetings, webinars or conferences is an easy way to meet people all over the world and can be more inclusive. Also, attending online events instead of physical meetings is a way to save time and budget for travel and accommodation and to reduce CO₂ emissions. Thus, more things can become possible because resources are saved.

As for preparing for networking at physical events, it is relevant to prepare beforehand including being aware of the possibilities and opportunities for networking that the host sets up as described in the practise abstract about that.

- Find out who you would like to approach.
- Attend before the start of the event;
- Participate in virtual coffee breaks in breakout rooms;
- Use the chat function to ask other participants to talk in breaks or after the event.

Participants from different age groups, geographic areas and sectors may react differently in terms of adapting to the conditions of online events and the digital skills vary. Furthermore, it is important to be aware that using digital tools may enlarge the gap between groups of people who are skilled and groups who are not very skilled and this can be a challenge when working together. It is important to engage, encourage and help each other as shared experiences online is better than working alone.

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2.66. Processes behind networking

According to the EC glossary networking is to: ‘use existing resources in your consortium to increase outreach on international, national, and regional level – for example, rely on your project partners’ already existing contacts and networks ...’ and the EURAKNOS project describes networking as: ‘use of the communication and dissemination materials at occasions where project partners are in direct interaction with the relevant networking partners, e.g. TN’s and initiatives with a common interest’.

To stimulate innovation when networking, it can be of use to get acquainted with parts of the processes or theories behind networking. There is substantial theory behind networking and the following is just a hint of what to be attentive of.

When stimulating innovation between people, there are roughly three modes/styles of communication:

- Transfer of knowledge and trying to convince the other person about your idea. There is the risk that you end up arguing about the best solution.
- Exchange of ideas and negotiation. You try to see what’s in it for the other person and to create a win-win situation.
- Co-creation with the other person. You try to find common ground and to see if you have shared ambitions and if you can create something together.

Trying to find common ground by co-creating is possibly the most energising mode of communication. You create something new together whereas the style with transfer of knowledge and convincing can be exhausting.

Co-creation can only take place in warm networks where the focus is on energy, connection and ambition. In warm networks, people share ambitions and pool their resources to innovate and to change together. Cold networks, on the other hand, are needed for structuring activities and for being accountable.

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2.67. Why carry out networking?

Networking is necessary to increase the outreach of your project. However, in order to appreciate the value of networking and thus, encourage project partners to do it, you need to know why it is relevant.

There are several complementing arguments for carrying out networking:

1. Meet people, talk to people, have a good atmosphere, feel safe, find trust and enthusiasm, have a good time;
2. Share ideas, learn from each other, exchange experiences, get inspired, build on personal ideas, co-create;
3. Find out who is working on the same subject, meet people who may have answers to ones' questions, get to know other peoples' interests, share experiences on similar interests, gather complementary skills, find a shared goal or ambition, feel connection about what everyone desires, reach greater impact.

The general aims or goals of doing networking are to get new connections, to deepen those connections and the understanding of the people you are networking with, and to use those connections to share, learn and inspire and maybe even co-create.

There are also obstacles to networking, such as the fact that may be different and conflicting ideas are being explored. Also, there may be cultural as well as linguistic differences, which makes it important to realize that networking is a trans-national experience. It may also be important to realise that everyone involved in networking want to have their contribution recognized.

A different goal of networking could be that you want to get contacts that you can visit in order to get new experiences and new knowledge, e.g. new countries, new farms, new industries.

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2.68. How to prepare for networking and get contact during meetings and events

To get the most out of networking, it is a good idea to be prepared before you participate in events where networking will be possible. This practice abstract is mainly relevant for face-to-face meetings, whereas online networking will be described in another practice abstract.

1. Consider, what the goal of networking is for you at this particular meeting.
 - a. Are you looking for partners for a new project that you plan to apply for?
 - b. Are you networking on behalf of a project you are already part of and the outcome of which you want to promote?
 - c. Are you looking for people to give input to your project e.g. in surveys or workshops?
 - d. Are you looking for new ideas within your area of work?
 - e. Other relevant goals?
2. Consider, how you want to approach potential networking partners.
 - a. Bring your business card and introduce yourself.
 - b. Bring printed material from your project and introduce your project.
 - c. Bring a tablet or pc and ask people to take the survey right there.
 - d. Have coffee together, sit together at meals or in breaks, go out in the evening to have time to talk.

When you are at a meeting or event, you can prepare beforehand who you want to contact for networking e.g. by looking at the list of participants. Also, during the meeting or conference you can realize that someone could be relevant when they give a presentation or present a poster, but also if they ask a question in relation to what you are interested in.

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2.69. Co-creation with different actors

Implementation of innovation in agriculture is complex as it requires professional knowledge from various fields of expertise combining “hard skills” and “soft skills”. In addition, a required innovation is often scattered in the minds of many concerned actors. Implementing an innovation thus requires collaboration between different actors from different sectors, areas of expertise and when this cuts across research, industry and practice, a clear understanding between actors is the ultimate prerequisite for transferring an innovation into practice.

If the innovation is addressed to critical areas, different actors may even have different perspectives on individual issues or even "hidden agendas". All this often leads to misunderstandings and disagreements between actors that hinder the creation or implementation of innovations.

The engaged multi-actor approach must aim to find the appropriate actors, bring them together in a context and create a suitable environment in which these actors can interact through the use of engaged co-creation methods, thereby complementing these scattered pieces of ideas by bringing individual views together.

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2.70. Demonstration as a tool for multi-stakeholder-based co-creation processes

Demonstration as an inherent part of multi-stakeholder-based co-creation processes help to create a better understanding between the different actors and stakeholders to support co-design and co-creation for innovation through demonstration.

This multi-stakeholder-based "social creation of innovation" in combination with prototypical approaches accompanied by demonstration differs from purely academic approaches and their frequent linear innovation models by involving all actors in the innovation processes from start to finish. Rather, all actors - including farmers and industry - should be involved with all their entrepreneurial skills, instead of seeing them as objects of study or only as targets for innovation outcomes.

It is therefore recommended to include a guided and moderated demonstration before a planned co-creation process. This demonstration can lead to an intensive discussion and exchange, in which the character of the actors can become very clear but can also lead to a so-called team feeling of the actors present. A demonstration activity is therefore, besides the transfer of information, an icebreaker, a teambuilding method, and a good start into a co-creation process.

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2.71. Holding a science and practice meeting as a multi-actor approach

In some TN projects, meetings between science and practice were held to better understand the benefits of MAA and thus develop guidelines for it.

As an introduction to such a facilitated discussion, a demonstration/innovation was favoured on which to base the discussion. The discussion group should consist of 5 to 15 people with as diverse backgrounds as possible, e.g. (scientists, extension workers, policy makers, farmers' association, NGOs, retailers), depending on the demonstration, the composition plays an essential role in the discussion. The meeting should not last longer than 4 hours, 2-3 hours have proven to be optimal, and the location of the discussion should be at or near the demonstration/innovation. The swot analysis was mainly used as a basis for the discussion and was applied to the demonstration or innovation presented. This provided an impetus and a basis for the stakeholders' discussion. The facilitator plays a crucial role here and should fully focus on the discussion round to include as many voices as possible. If stakeholder participation is too low, stakeholders need to be asked by the moderator to reveal their arguments. At the end of the discussion, a feedback round should be initiated to include every voice. At the end of the discussion, the facilitator should collect the feedback and announce the way forward after the meeting.

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2.72. What kind of competencies an innovation broker needs to fulfil her/his intermediary role?

Innovation brokers are the necessary intermediaries between TNs (broadly speaking: “science”) and end users (“farmers and foresters”), they help to mobilize innovation. Exploitation of the TN’s results depends highly on their preparedness, knowledge and competences.

Due to their diverse tasks (such as identifying problems and opportunities, broking relationships between disparate parts of system) innovation brokers in each sector need a comprehensive training and coaching. Not only training but also innovation coaching is important for brokers as soft skills can be developed effectively only with assessment of their progress.

TNs can do a lot to promote better preparedness of innovation brokers. TN knowledge reservoirs can serve as a basis of modular training materials. TNs can also ensure possibilities for coaching and workshop for the brokers along with development needs.

In general, based on experience, an innovation broker’s competence catalogue should consist of:

- comprehensive sector specific expertise, authenticity
- advanced communication, networking, negotiation and lobby skills, empathy
- community development skills
- business development skills
- system approach, project management and organisational skills
- leadership and problem solving skills, creativity
- overall picture about IT, logistics, marketing, online media
- up-to-date basic legal knowledge
- intermediate English

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2.73. Why is it important to involve innovation hubs in MA projects?

It is inconceivable to set up a multi actor projects without involvement of regional innovation hubs (built on committed offices, labs, or campus) as they are focal point for managing knowledge flow at regional levels. They are essential for facilitating interaction and knowledge exchange between different stakeholders at regional levels.

As innovation hubs are well connected and have a strategic overview concerning limitations and synergies, they play an important role in solving legal and technical obstacles of development. Functions of an innovation hub's composite role are:

- Communication and networking: giving visibility to the practice-based problems and solutions by attracting a wide range of actors within the regional innovation community and beyond (along synergies)
- Coaching and mediation: helping farmers, foresters and innovation brokers to redefine their experiences, complement their knowledge and to provide benefits from scientific results
- Advocacy: fighting for favourable conditions and supporting decision making processes
- Centre of activities

A major difficulty for innovation hubs is the lack of a universal tool kit to fulfil these expected functions. Especially a manual for stakeholder involvement is missing. The tools in EURAKNOS Explorer Guide can be well used to fill this gap. Although any manuals do not replace the clear definition of measurable objectives and values for each stakeholder group.

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2.74. End-users' involvement in the preliminary phases of innovation projects

Important activities that projects should plan are training sessions and workshops. They will enable the project to understand end-user needs and to disseminate outside the network. As farmers need to be involved from the preliminary phases of the project, these tools have proven to be an efficient strategy to engage with them. We suggest, if possible, creating a community of end-users before the start of the project. The Thematic Network (TN) Smart AKIS (<https://www.smart-akis.com/>) successfully involved traditional media and farmers from the beginning, successfully adjusting the originally planned path in favour of their needs.

Two efficient ways of collecting end-user inputs are questionnaires, and face-to-face interviews, which can then be discussed during the workshops. Their outcomes can be verified by establishing focus groups.

To have a successful end-user involvement, each project should create a space where the end-users can feel comfortable and are willing to participate. This can be done by

- Explaining how they can benefit from the project
- Organising an informal scenario while meeting them (with food and drink)
- Existing networks and groups should be utilised to further engage them
- Update them regularly during the lifetime of the project. They will feel that their input was valuable
- Contact them directly, this will implement their trust in the interviewer and project.
- Invite them to project events, they will feel involved.
- Cover and compensate end-user's costs while joining project events

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2.75. EU projects focused on livestock: Requests to policymakers

On the 9th September 2020, EURAKNOS hosted a cross exchange with 30 participants from 11 countries representing EU projects focused on livestock. Together, we discussed how to increase the impact and sustainability of projects and how policy/funding structures could support this.

It was considered difficult to build a self-sustaining network within the funded timeframe of projects. It was suggested funding should support a second phase for projects to focus on sharing the established knowledge and further animating their network. This limited sustainability was seemingly compounded by the start-and-stop nature of projects. To create a more dynamic and long-lasting progression of results, another idea was that new projects should inherit the work of previous projects working on a similar topic, so they can build on an existing network and knowledge base, rather than starting from scratch.

There was appetite for a common data platform to act as a permanent knowledge hub for practical agricultural knowledge. Participants were eager to see interactive functionality, e.g. forums, rating systems, and a directory to find relevant contacts and events according to topic. It was acknowledged that it would not be easy or cheap to create and maintain this online knowledge hub. However, individual projects incur costs to have their own website over a limited period, after which the knowledge might be lost. Individual projects also put enormous effort into achieving recognition. This funding and effort would perhaps be better invested in a central platform, which could become well-known within the agricultural community and become a trusted information source which gives credibility to new projects.

Find out more about a common data platform [here](#).

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2.76. Learning and collaborating across EU projects focused on livestock

On the 9th September 2020, EURAKNOS hosted a cross exchange between thematic networks and other EU H2020 projects focused on livestock farming. There were 30 participants from 11 countries who discussed how tools and knowledge acquired by projects can more effectively influence actions at the farm level.

Participants highlighted that interactivity and participatory tools were key to engaging farmers. Ideally in a face-to-face setting, but digital tools could also be used effectively such as messaging groups/forums, or video calls. However, digital connectivity in rural areas could be problematic for online engagement with farmers. Several attendees also hoped that funding structures could be adapted to reimburse farmers/advisors for their time and knowledge contributions.

The multi-actor approach was considered extremely important to achieving high impact. By engaging existing networks, and engaging farmers to act as ambassadors for the project can help ensure it produces practical, relevant resources which can be disseminated widely by project actors and external actors who perceive value in the project outputs.

Attendees emphasized the importance of linking with existing networks, primarily using established, trusted networks/contacts as intermediaries to disseminate resources to target users. Both impact and reach could be improved by translating resources into multiple languages for use in different countries, but the ability to do this within the project budget and timescale was limited.

The discussions in this cross exchange are complimentary to the recommendations in the EURAKNOS Explorer's Guide to Thematic Networks, available in different languages through our [website](#).

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2.77. How can stakeholder involvement be enhanced?

Multi-actor approach (MAA) is characteristic feature of thematic networks, it requires collaboration between different actors with complementary skills to co-create practice-based solution. For this reason, involvement of end-users (farmers, foresters, advisors and their communities) and active knowledge transfer in the team is crucial.

Experience shows that strict supporting schemes create a strong risk of “intervention without innovation” in the projects. Inflexible conditions reduce space for “creative failure” as expected results must be laid down in advance. In the recent system projects engage end-users who are usually chosen from outside of the consortium, based on presumed problems (not necessarily consistent with their identified problems), and different expectations cause poor engagement. Financial rules to involve end users as consortium member is risky due to sensible business goals, and limited resources, skills.

Enhanced stakeholder (especially end user) involvement is only possible with a more flexible support system in which:

- starting at the planning phase it is required to involve end user(s) together with innovation hubs (association, public body or research centre with possibility for coaching)
- regular follow up is incorporated to ensure re-integration of experiences during the project;
- more SME-friendly financial rules allow slight changes in goals if needed.

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2.78. Setting up innovation groups with farmers

In Thematic Networks, expert farmers and advisors develop good practices that can then be applied or inspire other users to trial new ideas and optimise their practice. The learnings from TN Organic Knowledge Network (OK-Net) EcoFeed (<https://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/>) presented in this Practice Abstract can inspire your own “harvest” of innovations.

The 11 Innovation Groups (IGs) of OK-Net EcoFeed are national or regional groups of up to 20 organic farmers, processors, breeders, researchers, value chain groups and farmer associations from across Europe. Workshops in the project countries stimulated innovation and paved the way for implementation.

Discuss relevant innovations during the first meeting and let the groups identify their specific characteristics and needs. The next meeting can be dedicated to potential innovations to be tested in the following years. Next to technical data, the EcoFeed IGs collected info on how knowledge is exchanged

More info on the IGs: <https://ok-net-ecofeed.eu/about-ok-net-ecofeed/innovation-groups/>

EURAKNOS podcast on EcoFeed: <https://open.spotify.com/episode/5AqhirMDpPQoC1pqy8Rs58>

Tips from the EcoFeed cross-exchange:

- Define clear targets for solutions as well as user profiles.
- Good facilitation is key.
- Let end users and other experts in the field validate the knowledge, through a set of criteria to assess stage of development, applicability, proven impact, added value, sustainability and repeatability of the practice in other regions.
- A feasibility study or cost-benefit analysis can be useful as well.

Short review of the CE: <https://euraknos.eu/news/cross-exchange-visit-web-based-agricultural-knowledge-exchange-to-support-and-inspire-production>

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2.79. The importance of the interaction between innovation projects

An aspect that each project should have from the beginning is a good connection with other projects. This will affect the quality of the outputs and productivity of teams.

Cooperation among projects might help to face another challenge: involve actors such as consumers and the agri-food chain. This is a gap that is highlighted also in the EURAKNOS project. While analysing 28 Thematic Networks (TN) funded under the H2020 programme, it has been noticed that this category is not involved in the multi actor concept.

Although there is not a formula that works for every project in terms of a good dissemination strategy, a worthy practice is to have clear view on the (sub) target groups, for example sector and education level, and what is important and interesting for them. Interaction among different projects might result in an exchange on best dissemination strategies and feedback mechanisms such as the use of Google analytics or consultations with end-users. In fact, according to the Operational Group (OG) “W&W leeks and cabbages” in Belgium and the coordinator of the Smart AKIS project (<https://www.smart-akis.com/>), Google analytics helped to target the dissemination because it gives a good indication of what information or knowledge is consulted.

Lastly, it is important to disseminate at the local level by using the channels that are most popular in a specific country. All the information must be shared in an easy-to-understand language.

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2.80.A national initiative to fight grapevine diseases

It is estimated that every year 4 to 5% of the French vineyard becomes unproductive due to decline. Grapevine decline is a multi-year decline in the productivity of the vine stock and/or its premature, brutal or progressive death due to a multiplicity of factors. It is on these factors that action must be taken. To do this, the French wine industry has committed itself to the State and launched in 2016 the National Plan for Vineyard decline. This initiative reflects the industry's desire to act at all levels, in a concerted manner with resources commensurate with the stakes to ensure the sustainability of French vineyards and the competitiveness of companies.

This national plan is organized around four complementary ambitions:

- Mobilize networks of actors to promote training and the transfer of good practices within the vineyard.
- Ensure the production of plant material in quantity and quality with the wine nursery.
- To coordinate observation networks of the vineyard.
- Promote interdisciplinary scientific research around five priority axes in response to the expectations of professionals.

To date, 21 research programs have been launched within the framework of this plan with 5 priority axes for an interdisciplinary and global research around: the relationship between yield and longevity in relation to physiological processes, the root eco-system and soil components, prevention and control of biological risks, control of plant material and socio-economic levers. The funding granted for all these projects amounts to 6.2 million euros.

More information on www.plan-deperissement-vigne.fr

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3. Conclusion and next steps

The EURAKNOS deliverable D5.11 was intensively discussed with all partners in the middle of the project and the approach was agreed. The main challenge was to avoid overlaps between the different PAs in one context, but still look at important issues from several sides. As all CEVs were conducted digitally due to the Covid 19 situation and could not be conducted physically as planned. The digital solutions saved time and travel costs, but the extra effort for training and delivery had to be taken into account.

In this group of 80 PAs, all partner-authors made a special effort to present the quintessence and the most important results of their CEV and/or to select the most important results of their preparatory work, complemented by the feedback they received through the end-user surveys sent to the CEV participants. The main objective of the 80 additional PAs EOP was to provide user-friendly short texts on best practices and to inform about EURAKNOS activities and results in order to facilitate the knowledge flow on innovative and practical projects from the beginning to the end of the project. This format of EIP Agri allows farmers, advisors, researchers and all other EU stakeholders to exchange and contribute to the important elements of the implementation of the project methods.

Besides the strong commitment of the authors and the difficult conditions created by Covid 19, a very good and informative product has been produced. The format of the practice abstracts lends itself perfectly to the aim of compiling short summaries of lessons learned for the staff of future thematic networks. Due to the assumption that the target group must be proficient in English, translations into the national languages were not sought. The practice summaries in this case are a bundling of many discussions from different actors sharing experiences. The abstracts are thus for orientation and discussion and are empirical data from projects, workshops or conferences and not scientific papers with sources and citations.

The bundling of abstracts has shown how important the exchange of experiences is and how exciting and highly effective this exchange will be for further projects and methods. Whilst TNs often focus on the exchange of best practices between farmers, foresters etc – there is much to be gained from exchanging experiences with other members of project consortia. EURAKNOS has produced many useful materials to help guide future thematic network projects, including these practice abstracts presented in this report. It is essential that this co-creation of knowledge continues into the future; every thematic network should include honest reflections on its strengths and weaknesses in the reporting and opportunities must be made available for the exchange of experiences. Experience gained in the course of a project in terms of methodology and implementation are fundamental for the development of future projects. There needs to be more focus on self-reflection of methodology within a project, and greater opportunities for the exchange and presentation of lessons learnt. The technical work is absolutely important, but without the necessary tools and guidance it will not be effective and learning from mistakes or good approaches will be lost. Therefore, we recommend further self-reflection in the projects and more opportunities to exchange ideas about how to address the challenges faced. These practical excerpts offer valuable insight into the experiences that exist in the Eu project world, which primarily concern the need for greater means to reach and impact target users.

